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infrastructure PLUS**

Water use efficiency (WUE) of ecosystems and resilience to drought

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Contributors:

Nikolaos Nikolaidis, Dionissis Efstathiou, Maria Lilli, Evangelia Koukianaki, Antonia Maragkaki
Technical University of Crete

Christian Poppe Terán, Bibi Sarwat Naz, Harrie-Jan Hendricks-Franssen, Harry Vereecken
Forschungszentrum Juelich

Martyn Futter
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

Bradley Matthews, Karl Knaebel, Gisela Pröll
Environment Agency Austria

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Executive Summary

The world faces many Grand Challenges including those posed by climate change, biodiversity loss, and water and soil pollution. These multiple stressors act simultaneously over a range of temporal and spatial scales, resulting in significant loss of ecosystem services that eventually affect societal well-being and humanity. While immediate impacts sometimes receive considerable attention, little is known about their long-term and systemic effects and cross-scale interactions. Closing these knowledge gaps requires an improved, transdisciplinary understanding of the multifaceted environmental system, in order to develop appropriate mitigation measures (Mirtl et al., 2018). The Whole System Approach in eLTER PLUS has a clear position to develop scientific, practical and conceptual innovations for addressing environmental resilience and sustainable social and ecological systems. The eLTER Whole System Approach encompasses the Earth system and related domains/disciplines from geosphere to hydrosphere, biosphere and socio-econosphere to atmosphere.

The eLTER-PLUS Project, Work Package 8 aimed to explore how long-term biodiversity, biogeochemistry, hydrology and socio-ecology data from the eLTER network can provide the necessary holistic understanding of the ecosystem response to environmental and societal pressures. WP8 focuses on assessing the capacity of data provision of eLTER Sites to evaluate environmental impacts using the Whole System Approach. In particular task 8.3 aimed to improve the knowledge of the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience. Data from 10 well-instrumented sites that cross climatic, geological and socio-ecological regions were used to test resilience indicators. The overall objective of Task 8.3 is to address the following scientific question: *“What is the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience, and the relationships between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience?”*

Field data and integrated models were used to calculate the ecosystem WUE of sites to:

- Assess the impact of drought events on the WUE of ecosystems
- Analyze the resilience of the ecosystems with respect to their ability to recover single & multiple droughts
- Assess the relationship between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience and develop mitigation measures for drought adverse impacts
- Assess the strengths and weaknesses of the RI-design to derive resilience indicators

Our methodology followed a three-prong approach:

- **Flux tower Eddy Covariance long term data** were used to assess the impact of droughts on WUE. Ten well instrumented sites with good availability of long-term data as well as good spatial distribution covering the whole European continent were selected for this analysis.
- Two **integrated models, 1D-ICZ and CLM5.0**, that simulate the plant-soil-water system were used to assess the relationship between WUE and soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience. For this analysis, in addition to flux tower data, data regarding vegetation, soil stocks of C, N, P, K, lysimeter chemistry, atmospheric chemistry and fertilization loadings were utilized to calibrate the models. Three sites (Zöbelboden, Austria; Hyytiälä, Finland; Svartberget, Sweden) were selected with the best available data.
- Finally, two **watershed scale models, SWAT and INCA** were used to assess the impact of droughts at the basin scale. Additional hydrologic data and river and groundwater chemistry data were required for the calibration of the models. Two different sites, Koiliaris CZO in Greece and Svartberget in Sweden were used for the simulations of SWAT and INCA-N respectively.

The methodology aimed at assessing how forested ecosystems respond to drought across Europe using flux tower eddy covariance field data and then examine if 1D integrated models and

watershed models can capture the ecosystem response. Given that very few sites have long time series of flux tower data, this study is assessing the capability of integrated and watershed scale models to reconstruct historical impacts of drought events in a historical reanalysis exercise.

Flux tower Eddy Covariance Analysis – The monthly Gross Primary Production (GPP), Evapotranspiration (ET) and water use efficiency (WUE) flux tower data along with the PDSI were used to determine drought indices for each site for various drought periods and then evaluate the Response and Resilience Indices. Given that there was no correlation between Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI) and WUE or ET, in this study drought indices were defined based on the response of GPP, the productivity of the forested ecosystem. The impact of drought on GPP, was estimated using the **Drought Response Index** and the **Resilience Index**. The Drought Response Index is the relationship between the Drought Index and the GPP Response Index. The Drought Index is defined as (Number of months that PDSI is less than -2.0) * (Average PDSI) during those months) and the GPP Response Index is the total of monthly GPP the month after the drought period for a year. So, the Drought Response Index shows what was the total GPP productivity the year after a moderate to extreme drought occurred. The trend of the relationship between the Drought Index and the GPP Response Index illustrates the trend of the ecosystem response to drought events. Drought Resilience Index is the maximum GPP during the year after the end of the drought to the max GPP during the years without drought. The objective of this analysis was to identify the response of forested ecosystem productivity across the continent to drought events as well as the resilience of the ecosystems to drought (meaning that they are capable of achieving maximum growth after the drought event).

There were 25 extreme drought events realized at the 10 stations that allowed the determination of the drought indices. The number of consecutive months with PDSI below -2 range from 2 in Brasschaat to 29 in Yatir while the average PDSI during these periods ranged from -2.0 at Zöbelboden to -3.16 at Renon. The Drought Index ranged from -4.36 to -81.78, however only 4 events had values less than -40 across all sites. The GPP Response Index ranged from 676 g m⁻² y⁻¹ at Yatir to 2,243 g m⁻² y⁻¹ at Wüstebach. Only the two events at Yatir had an annual growth less than 900 g m⁻². The resilience Index ranged from 0.58 to 1.0, while 22 out of the 25 events the index was higher than 0.7 meaning that it reached 70% of the non-drought maximum growth.

The results of this analysis showed that the GPP Response is decreasing as the Drought duration and intensity are increasing (Figure ES-1). This can be observed both at the European level (including all the events together) as well as at the regional levels. However, it should be noted that at the low drought index events we have a high variability of the GPP response. On the other hand, we do not observe any significant trends in the impact of the intensity of drought on the Resilience of the system to reach maximum growth for Europe as a whole. It appears that all forested ecosystems are quite resilient to drought events regardless of the location. These results can be confirmed if we plot drought events greater than -25 drought index (Figure ES-2). Eliminating the less intense 17 events, the relationship between drought index and GPP response becomes more pronounced (R^2 of 0.63), decreasing at a rate of 138 g m⁻² y⁻¹ for every -10 units increase of the drought index. While the resilience index does not show any trend with the average resilience index to be at 75%.

It is important to mention at this point that the EC-GPP fluxes of Zöbelboden (not measured but derived from the EC measurements using flux partitioning) are not derived with the same methodology as the other sites that follow the ICOS methodology. The EC-GPP fluxes are responding to the short-term and average monthly dynamics, because the GPP model is being fitted to each month using data from all years. This means that the EC-GPP fluxes aren't suitable for analysis looking at drought response and recovery. For this, we would need to parameterize for each month of each year, or be even more resolved than this, which most sites could do but for the Zöbelboden site this wasn't possible due to low levels of data retention. With such parameterization in time, one can implicitly derive legacy effects of drought. However, in a certain analysis that was conducted by the Environment Agency of Austria, such dynamics cannot be

seen, and if they were seen it is simply to coincidence with the driving weather variables R_g and VPD. Despite these concerns, it was chosen to keep these two datapoint in the analysis because the results were consistent with the response of other sites in central Europe. In addition, the Drought Index values were low (less than -25) and did not affect the trend analysis. On the other hand, the GPP estimates can be used for the calibration of the models for the Zöbelboden site.

Figure ES-1. Comparison of the Drought Index with a) GPP Response Index and b) Resilience Index for all the sites and drought events.

Figure ES-2. Comparison of the Drought Index with a) GPP Response Index and b) Resilience Index for all the sites and drought events greater than -25 of drought index.

Integrated Model Analysis With the 1D-ICZ

Zöbelboden – The 1D-ICZ model successfully simulated the GPP of the Zöbelboden forested ecosystem along with the growth limitations, the total C and N biomass, the nutrient uptake, the C and N stock of leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. Figure ES-3 compares the monthly GPP flux measurements and the simulated GPP by 1D-ICZ model over time. The RMSE between the monthly simulated and field data was 80.12 gC m^{-2} while the annual RMSE was 247.55 gC m^{-2} (or 22% of the mean annual GPP). Finally, the difference between the cumulative field and modelled GPP was $3,302.33 \text{ gC m}^{-2}$ which corresponds to 10% closure. These results suggest that the 1D-ICZ model is capable of simulating GPP while accounting correctly for the limiting factors, the nutrient fluxes, temperature and PAR. The WUE was estimated by using the simulated GPP and the simulated ET over the simulated period 1996-2020. WUE varies between 1.95 to 5.45 kg m^{-3} and has an annual average of 3.67 kg m^{-3} and the results were similar to flux tower estimates.

Figure ES-3. Comparison of simulated monthly GPP with flux tower data (2014-2020) at Zöbelboden.

The 1D-ICZ model was able to simulate the solute transport of F, K, Na, NH_4N , NO_3N and SO_4S quite well while for the simulations of Ca, Mg and H^+ the model was over or under predicting. Deposition data were available for Ca, K, Mg, Na, NH_4N , NO_3N , H^+ , and SO_4S but not for F. It was assumed that F originates entirely from precipitation, and thus the input values for boundary conditions were set to be the same order of magnitude as the soil measurements. The reason why solutes Ca and Mg could not be simultaneously simulated properly has to do with the weathering formulation of the model. The sub-model SAFE that simulates weathering processes includes six minerals in which one of them is dolomite and it does not include one of the primary minerals of Zöbelboden geology, limestone. If limestone was to be added in the model, the weathering of dolomite will simulate Mg concentrations and then the weathering of limestone will provide the additional Ca needed for the simulation of Ca. This will also correct the pH simulation. In the near future we intend to modify the code of sub-model SAFE and the process of limestone weathering.

Drought analysis was conducted using Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI). PDSI was calculated for the period of time 1996-2020. Drought impact to plant growth was assessed by estimating the Drought Index, the GPP Response Index and the Resilience Index for the extreme drought events ($\text{PDSI} < -2.0$) during the 25-year simulation period.

The analysis of drought for the period 1996-2020 showed that drought is directly impacting GPP. In particular, the GPP response and resilience were positively correlated to the Drought Index. More precisely, when the severity of drought increases the GPP response and the resilience rise. These relationships are quite strong as shown by the correlation between the Drought versus GPP Response Index ($R^2=0.73$) and the Drought and the Resilience Index ($R^2=0.67$). These results suggest that the forested ecosystem of Zöbelboden is responding in a positive way to extreme drought events and the ecosystem is resilient. This trend contrasts the negative trend between the Drought and the GPP response for the 10 sites using the flux tower data. However, focusing on the Zöbelboden data revealed an increase in GPP response index with increasing drought. One of the reasons for this difference is that all but one of the Zöbelboden droughts from 1996-2020 have Drought Index values less than -30, which means that they are in the low intensity drought, an area with great variability in the GPP response. Moreover, the extremely complex topography

surrounding the tower at Zöbelboden render the site conditions non-ideal for eddy covariance measurements of net turbulent forest atmosphere exchange. Models for the LTER site Zöbelboden were fitted to obtain complete estimates of NEE, GEP & Reco from 2014-2021 by using the daytime partitioning method according to Lasslop et al. (2010). Due to the low data retention (<10 %) for flag 0 data needed for partitioning, the fits were aggregated over the whole period rather than using moving and expanding windows. Therefore, the temporal variations in the dataset were driven by the weather parameters and an average monthly phenology over the 2014-2021 period. Furthermore, even with this method, which should eliminate night-time bias in NEE measurements, the average NEP value is very high for the Zöbelboden site.

A scenario of addition of organic matter (compost) was performed in order to assess the impact of soil structure and fertility to WUE. According to the 1D-ICZ model, the litterfall varies between 6.1 and 14.6 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ and has an average value of 9.6 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹. So, for this scenario the addition of 10 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ that is evenly distributed during the months between October to January (2.5 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) was selected. The additional soil organic matter (SOM) was added in the form of compost. The results illustrate how SOM addition improves soil structure and soil dynamics by increasing the amount of carbon sequestered in the upper soil layer, the water stable aggregate (WSA) content and by decreasing the bulk density of the soil and the porosity which in turn increase the water holding capacity of the soil.

Hyytiälä – The 1D-ICZ model successfully simulated the GPP of the Hyytiälä forested ecosystem along with the growth limitations, the total C and N biomass, the nutrient uptake, the C and N stock of leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae (Figure ES-4). The primary limiting factors of growth were P and N. The RMSE between the monthly simulated and field data was 67.38 gC m⁻² while the annual RMSE was 389.30 gC m⁻² (or 35% of the mean annual GPP). Finally, the difference between the cumulative field and modelled GPP was 12,288.59 gC m⁻² which corresponds to 3% closure. These results suggest that the 1D-ICZ model is capable of simulating GPP while accounting correctly for the limiting factors, the nutrient fluxes, temperature and PAR. It was also shown that the 1D-ICZ model was able to simulate very successfully the solutes IC, TOC, TN, PO₄P and H⁺ of both catchments of Hyytiälä site. The WUE over the years varies between 1.85 to 7.82 kg m⁻³ and has an average value of 4.82 kg m⁻³. Finally, drought analysis results are similar to Zöbelboden and suggest that drought is directly impacting the GPP response and resilience in a positive way. More precisely, when the severity of drought increases so does the response and so does the resilience. These relationships are quite strong and the R² for the Drought versus GPP Response Index is 0.74 and for the Resilience Index 0.76. These results suggest that the forested ecosystem of Hyytiälä is responding in a positive way to extreme drought events and the ecosystem is resilient.

Figure ES-4. Comparison of simulated GPP with flux tower measurements (1996-2020) at Hyytiälä.

Svartberget – The field data we had to calibrate the model were the flux tower measurement of GPP and the stream chemistry data to calibrate the geochemistry. There were deposition measurements of K, NO₃N, NH₄N and PO₄P available. However, the values were orders of magnitude higher than expected compared to Zöbelboden and Hyytiälä precipitation chemistry data. These high deposition rates made it impossible to calibrate the stream chemistry, so it was necessary to decrease these values by 3 to 4 orders of magnitude. The calibration of the model regarding the GPP evolution with time (Figure ES-5) was not good primarily because of problems in the deposition data that affect growth limitations and biomass production as well as the lack of other required data (especially for soil initial conditions and soil structure data).

Figure ES-5. Comparison of simulated GPP with flux tower measurements (2014-2020) at Svartberget.

Integrated Model Analysis with CLM5.0

Zöbelboden – CLM5-BGC was able to capture the overall seasonal variations and ET changes in spring and autumn. The GPP flux was more accurately simulated at this site, with well agreeing minimal winter GPP values of CLM5-BGC with observations (Figure ES-6). However, summer peaks of both, ET and GPP are not well simulated, showing underestimations of GPP and

overestimations of ET. This may be due to more structural problems CLM5-BGC has with simulating the eco-hydrology of karstic sites, or default vegetation parameters misrepresenting summer peak conditions. In future, seasonal decomposition of the time-series and multi-variate analysis of seasonal environmental factors might yield insights how to improve the CLM5-BGC model at the Zöbelboden site.

Figure ES-6: Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) GPP (y-axis, in gC month^{-1}) at Zöbelboden. Data for this site and variable was available from 2014 until 2018.

Hyytiälä – In the case of the Hyytiälä site, ET peaks in summer are modelled better than for Zobelboden, but winter ET is still generally underestimated by CLM5-BGC. On top of that, there is an apparent trend in the observed ET that is not simulated by CLM5-BGC. The trend is also there for the observed GPP variable, and again not evident from the CLM5-BGC simulations (Figure ES-7). For Hyytiälä, future research will look at the representation of long-term CO_2 and VPD influence and evaluate the specific GPP and ET response to those long-term trends in the model.

Figure ES-7: Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) GPP (y-axis, in gC month^{-1}) at Hyytiälä. Data for this site and variable was available from 1996 until 2018.

Svartberget – The simulations of Svartberget in CLM5-BGC are showing well-fitting variation and summer peaks of ET when compared to in-situ observations. As with the other sites, winter ET is generally underestimated. Similarly, GPP is also well modelled at this site, but shows underestimated summer peaks (Figure ES-8). For a more detailed analysis, longer time series are of need, so that potential long-term trends and systematic modelling errors can be estimated robustly.

Figure ES-8: Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) GPP (y-axis, in gC month⁻¹) at Svartberget. Data for this site and variable was available from 2014 until 2018.

Watershed Model Analysis

WUE modelling at the Koiliaris CZO using SWAT – In this work we analysed the results from a simulation of Koiliaris CZO for an irrigated Orange grove landuse from 1980-2020. The monthly GPP, ET, WUE and PDSI simulated time series are presented in Figure ES-9. The average annual simulated GPP was 7.9 kgC m⁻² while the average annual ET was 957 mm y⁻¹. The average WUE was determined to 9.5 kgC m⁻³ of water. The PDSI for the region determined that we had eight medium to extreme drought events (PDSI less than -2). The PDSI and the GPP time series were used to determine the drought response and resilience indices for the site. Table 5 presents the determination of the drought indices for the eight extreme drought events realized between 1980-2020. The number of consecutive months with PDSI below -2 range from 4 to 24 while the average PDSI during these periods ranged from -2.1 to -3.3. The Drought Index ranged from -8.2 to -59, with three events to have values less than -30. The GPP Response Index ranged from 7.1 kg m⁻² y⁻¹ to 12 kg m⁻² y⁻¹. The resilience Index ranged from 0.56 to -1.0, while the index of three out of the eight events was higher than 0.7 meaning that it reached 70% of the non-drought maximum growth. Both the GPP Response and the Resilience Indices are not being affected by the increasing drought duration and intensity. Irrigation is alleviating any possible drought effects. The results are consistent with the flux tower drought response we obtained from the other ecosystems.

Figure ES-9. Simulated time series of GPP, ET, WUE and PDSI for an orange grove at Koiliaris CZO.

WUE modelling at the Svartberget Catchment using INCA-N – The INCA-N simulations were able to satisfactorily reproduce flows and instream nitrogen concentrations. Model results suggested a decline in actual evapotranspiration during the period of simulation. This was corroborated by the ICOS latent heat data. The model also suggested a decline in net plant nitrogen uptake. This, and its consequences for forest carbon accumulation, are worthy of further investigation.

Figure ES-10. a) Latent heat fluxes (blue) and catchment-scale modelled actual evapotranspiration (orange) and b) N uptake and immobilisation over time.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the synthesis of the results presented above, several overarching conclusions and recommendations can be made:

1. Flux tower data analysis indicates a significant resilience to moderate to extreme drought events of forested ecosystems throughout Europe. In addition, the GPP Response is decreasing as the drought duration and intensity are increasing. This can be observed both at the European level (including all the events together) as well as at the regional levels. However, it should be noted that at the low drought index events we have a high variability of the GPP response. These results can be confirmed if we plot drought events greater than -25 drought index. Eliminating the less intense 17 events, the relationship between drought index and GPP response becomes more pronounced (R^2 of 0.63), decreasing at a rate of $138 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for every -10 units increase of the drought index. The resilience index does not show any trend with the average resilience index to be at 75%.
2. It is important to mention at this point that the EC-GPP fluxes of Zöbelboden (not measured but derived from the EC measurements using flux partitioning) are not derived with the same methodology as the other sites that follow the ICOS methodology. The EC-GPP fluxes are responding to the short-term and average monthly dynamics, because the GPP model is being fitted to each month using data from all years. This means that the EC-GPP fluxes aren't suitable for analysis looking at drought response and recovery. For this, we would need to parameterize for each month of each year, or be even more resolved than this, which most sites could do but for the Zöbelboden site this wasn't possible due to low levels of data retention. With such parameterization in time, one can implicitly derive legacy effects of drought. However, in a certain analysis that was conducted by the Environment Agency of Austria, such dynamics cannot be seen, and if they were seen it is simply to coincidence with the driving weather variables R_g and VPD. Despite these concerns, it was chosen to keep these two datapoint in the analysis because the results were consistent with the response of other sites in central Europe. In addition, the Drought Index values were low (less than -25) and did not affect the trend analysis. On the other hand, the GPP estimates can be used for the calibration of the models for the Zöbelboden site.
3. The 1D-ICZ model is capable of simulating successfully the primary production of the forested ecosystems and their Water Use Efficiency. In addition, it can correctly simulate the geochemistry of the unsaturated zone as well as the concentrations of solutes leaching to groundwater and the stream. These simulations are subject to appropriate deposition time series, soil characteristics and nutrient fractionation in the various aggregate sizes. These data constrain the model and assure proper simulation of the biogeochemical processes. Missing or erroneous data result in poor simulations (the case of Svartberget).
4. It is highly recommended that sites incorporate measurements of water stable fractionation procedures, carbon and nutrient content in the different fractions of the water stable aggregates. In this way the soil carbon and nutrient sequestration and soil structure module of the ICZ model can be constraint with field data and increase the validity of both the plant module as well as the geochemical module results.
5. The CLM5-BGC was able to capture the overall seasonal variations and ET changes for all three sites. The GPP flux was more accurately simulated at the Zöbelboden site compared to the other two.
6. Overall, this study showed that field scale models can adequately simulate the impacts of drought on forested ecosystems. Both the 1D-ICZ and the CLM5.0 models were able to

simulate the field data as well as identify the needs in additional measurements at each site. This information is very valuable for the development of the eLTER RI in terms of defining Standard Operating variables necessary to address the Whole System Approach.

7. Both the SWAT and the INCA-N watershed scale models were also able to simulate plant growth in agricultural and forested ecosystems respectively and assess the impact of drought on the water use efficiency of the vegetation. The results are consistent with the flux tower analysis, suggesting that biogeochemical models can be used successfully to address changes in ecosystem services as part of the Whole System Approach.
8. All of the data needed to setup and calibrate the INCA-N model could be obtained from publicly accessible open data sources. However, it was not possible to obtain all the necessary data from any single data provider. This highlight both the challenges and opportunities when attempting to work from a WAILS (whole system) perspective. The need to source, manipulate and apply data from multiple sources is a challenge but it is a road map for the opportunities for virtual co-location when data from multiple sources are presented in a single portal. Further exploration of the possibilities for using portals to combine site level data from multiple disparate sources could lead to more timely modelling results and decision support.

1. Introduction

The world faces many Grand Challenges including those posed by climate change, biodiversity loss, and water and soil pollution. These multiple stressors act simultaneously over a range of temporal and spatial scales, resulting in significant loss of ecosystem services that eventually affects societal well-being and humanity. While immediate impacts sometimes receive considerable attention, little is known about their long-term and systemic effects and cross-scale interactions. Closing these knowledge gaps requires an improved, transdisciplinary understanding of the multifaceted environmental system, in order to develop appropriate mitigation measures (Mirtl et al., 2018). The Whole System Approach in eLTER PLUS has a clear position to develop scientific, practical and conceptual innovations for addressing environmental resilience and sustainable social and ecological systems. The eLTER Whole System Approach encompasses the Earth system and related domains/disciplines from geosphere to hydrosphere, biosphere and socio-econosphere to atmosphere. One of the objectives of the eLTER-PLUS project is to test the Whole System Approach at both the local and at the continental scales. Work Package 8 addresses the local scale while WP9 focuses on the continental scale. The task 8.3 studies components of the Whole System Approach at the site level, the hydrological and biogeochemical cycles and the way the vegetation responds to drought.

WP8 explored how long-term biodiversity, biogeochemistry, hydrology and socio-ecology data of the eLTER network can provide the necessary holistic understanding of the ecosystem response to environmental (e.g. land use and climate change) and societal pressures. WP8 focused on the capacity of the design, data quality and data services of eLTER Sites. This was delivered and synthesized through the five tasks of the work package. WP8 focused on both site and catchment scales as well as on a common theme “extreme events”. The task 8.3 aimed to improve the knowledge of the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience, and to understand relationships between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience. Data from 10 well-instrumented sites that cross climatic, geological and socio-ecological regions were used to test resilience indicators, such as WUE, nutrient use efficiency, soil structure and function. This analysis used 1D (plot) or catchment scale integrated models that consider the water-soil-plant system.

Integrated models were used to calculate the ecosystem WUE and simulate sites to:

- Assess the impact of drought events on the WUE of ecosystems
- Analyze the resilience of the ecosystems with respect to their ability to recover single & multiple droughts
- Assess the relationship between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience and develop mitigation measures for drought adverse impacts
- Assess the strengths and weaknesses of the RI-design to derive resilience indicators

The overall objective of Task 8.3 was to address the following scientific question:

“What is the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience, and the relationships between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience?”

2. Methodology

2.1. Time series analysis of flux tower data

The objective of this analysis is to assess the impact of droughts on WUE using time series obtained from **Flux tower Eddy Covariance long-term data that measure the CO₂ and H₂O net flux**. In particular, flux tower Eddy Covariance measurements of Net Ecosystem Production (NEE) and its partition of Gross Primary Production (GPP) as well as latent heat flux (ET) at the ecosystem level from the FLUXNET and ICOS Networks were obtained. Further input data were meteorological variables, precipitation and soil moisture from the same stations.

The selection of the stations followed a multi-step process and it was based on the availability of long-term data as well as their spatial distribution so the whole European continent is covered. This resulted in the selection of 10 sites. In collaboration with Task 8.1, 8.2 and 8.4, we examined the availability of required data and identified potential sites that cover the continent spatially and have flux towers operating at the sites. Figure 2-1 presents the spatial distribution of the selected 10 forested sites that have flux tower instrumentation and the Koiliaris Critical Zone Observatory that will be used to assess WUE at the watershed scale.

The second stage was to include the data coverage and identify the sites that have long coverage, ideally of 30 years duration. Table 2-1 presents the data coverage and the source datasets of 10 forested stations from the initial list. Given that the other sites did not have readily available data or the duration was too short, it was decided to work with the 10 stations listed in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1. Data coverage and source of 10 forested stations with flux tower instrumentation

Site Name	Dataset	Data Coverage	
		Start	End
Brasschaat, Belgium	ICOS	1996-01-01	2020-12-31
Rollesbroich, Germany	ICOS	2011-01-01	2020-12-31
Selhausen Germany	ICOS	2011-01-01	2020-12-31
Wüstebach, Germany	ICOS	2012-01-01	2020-12-31
Hyytiälä, Finland	ICOS	1996-01-01	2020-12-31
Yatir, Israel	ICOS	2000-01-01	2020-12-31
Renon, Italy	ICOS	1999-01-01	2020-12-31
Collelongo-Selva Piana, Italy	FLUXNET	1996-01-01	2020-12-31
Svartberget, Sweden	ICOS	2014-01-01	2020-12-31
Zöbelboden, Austria	Site Owner	2014-06-01	2020-12-31

The datasets were obtained from:

- Warm Winter 2020 source: ICOS
- FLUXNET source: eLTER Repository
- eLTER source: eLTER Repository

The variables obtained and analysed in this phase of the work are the following (Ref: <https://fluxnet.org/data/fluxnet2015-dataset/fullset-data-product/>):

- **Gross Primary Production**, from Daytime partitioning method: GPP_DT_VUT_REF (gC m⁻² d⁻¹)
- **Net Ecosystem Exchange**, using Variable Ustar Threshold (VUT) for each year, reference selected on the basis of the model efficiency (MEF): NEE_VUT_REF (gC m⁻² d⁻¹)
- Quality flag for NEE_VUT_REF (fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data): NEE_VUT_REF_QC

Figure 2-1. Spatial distribution of high priority eLTER sites.

- **Latent heat flux**, gapfilled using MDS method: LE_F_MDS ($W\ m^{-2}$) average from half-hourly data
- Quality flag for LE_F_MDS, LE_CORR, LE_CORR25, and LE_CORR75 (fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data): LE_F_MDS_QC
- **Air temperature**, gapfilled using MDS method: TA_F_MDS (deg C) average from half-hourly data
- Quality flag for TA_F_MDS fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data: TA_F_MDS_QC
- **Ecosystem Respiration**, from Daytime partitioning method: RECO_DT_VUT_REF ($g\ C\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$)

- **Soil water content**, gapfilled with MDS (numeric index “#” increases with the depth, 1 is shallowest)
- SWC_F_MDS_1 / SWC_F_MDS_1_QC, SWC_F_MDS_2 / SWC_F_MDS_2_QC, SWC_F_MDS_3 / SWC_F_MDS_3_QC, SWC_F_MDS_4 / SWC_F_MDS_4_QC, SWC_F_MDS_5 / SWC_F_MDS_5_QC

The following procedure was used for data processing:

- Retrieve raw data (raw_data)
- Implement qc on data (where applicable): data = raw_data x qc_factor
- Smooth data: 30 days rolling mean
- Find long-term trends: Time series decomposition

Appendix I presents the data manipulation procedures for the time series analysis. Time series trend analysis and data decomposition was performed for all the stations.

In addition, the Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI) and the Soil Moisture Deficit Index (SMDI) were calculated for the drought analysis. Finally, the normalized GPP and latent heat fluxes were used to calculate the Water Use Efficiency (WUE). The meteorologic drought was estimated based on PDSI and the hydrologic drought using the Soil Moisture Deficit Index by Narasimhan and Srinivasan (2005), which is used for agricultural drought monitoring.

$$SMDI_k = 0.5 \times SMDI_{k-1} + \frac{SD_k}{50}$$

$$SD_{i,j} = \frac{SW_{i,j} - MSW_j}{MSW_j - minSW_j} \times 100, \text{ if } SW_{i,j} = MSW_j$$

- $SD_{i,j}$: soil water deficit (%)
 $SW_{i,j}$: mean weekly soil water available in the soil profile (mm)
 MSW_j : long-term median available soil water in the soil profile (mm)
 $maxSW_j$: long-term maximum available soil water in the soil profile (mm)
 $minSW_j$: long-term minimum available soil water in the soil profile (mm)
 i : years
 j : 1–52 weeks
 k : 1–52 * i weeks

The impact of drought on GPP, ET and WUE was estimated using the **Drought Response Index** and the **Resilience Index**.

The **Drought Response Index** is the relationship between the **Drought Index** and the **GPP Response Index**. The Drought Index is defined as follows:

$$\text{Drought Index} = (\text{Number of months that PDSI is less than } -2.0) * (\text{Average PDSI during those months})$$

The **GPP Response Index** is the total of monthly GPP the month after the drought period for a year. So, the **Drought Response Index shows what was the total GPP productivity the year after a moderate to extreme drought occurred**. The trend of the relationship between the **Drought Index** and the **GPP Response Index illustrates the trend of the ecosystem response to drought events**.

Drought Resilience Index is the maximum GPP during the year after the end of the drought to the max GPP during the years without drought.

The monthly GPP, ET and WUE flux tower data along with the PDSI were used to determine these indices for each site for various drought periods and then evaluate the Response and Resilience Indices for each site as well as for regions.

The objective of this analysis is to identify the trends of forested ecosystems across the continent to drought events as well as the resilience of the ecosystems to drought (meaning that they are capable of achieving substantial growth after the drought event).

2.2. WUE modelling with 1D models

The objective of this analysis will be to study the plant-soil-water system and assess the relationship between WUE and soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience. We will use two models the **1D-ICZ** and the **CLM5.0** models. For this analysis, we will also need information regarding the vegetation, soil stocks of C, N, P, K, lysimeter chemistry, atmospheric chemistry and fertilization loadings.

Brief description of the one-dimensional Integrated Critical Zone (1D-ICZ) model – The 1D-ICZ is a tractable mathematical model that links soil aggregate formation and soil structure development to nutrient dynamics, plant nutrition, and water flow and mass transport (Giannakis et al., 2017; Kotronakis et al., 2017). The model simulates and quantifies four of the main soil ecosystem functions (biomass production, carbon/nutrient sequestration in relation to soil structure, water filtration and bacteria-fungi dynamics) by accounting for interactions between water flow, solute transport, soil structure dynamics, carbon and nutrient dynamics and plant biomass production. The 1D-ICZ model is comprised of sub-modules (HYDRUS, CAST, PROSUM and chemical weathering and bioturbation) linked together to simulate the interactions of biotic and abiotic processes above and below ground in order to simulate predominant soil functions as well as the dynamics of soil hydraulic conductivity and water holding capacity. The heart of the model is the CAST module (Stamati et al., 2013) that simulates the dynamics of soil formation (aggregation and disaggregation), soil structure and nutrients. Soil structure (e.g. macro-aggregate content) depends strongly on Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) content which in turn influences soil hydraulic properties. The CAST model has been applied widely all over the world simulating the evolution of carbon sequestration and soil structure dynamics from the fore field of the Damma Glacier in the Swiss Alps, to China's Black soils, to Cretan Soils, US Mid-West soils to Burkina Faso soil restoration experiments (Panakoulia et al., 2017; Andrianaki et al., 2017; Apostolakis et al., 2017; Li et al., 2017).

The 1D-ICZ model is the first attempt in the scientific literature to simulate key processes necessary for integrated understanding of soil functioning. The scientific advancement made through the development of the 1D-ICZ model is the rigorous simulation and quantification of important soil functions such as the cycling of nutrients (C, N and P) while accounting for the effect of soil structure; biomass production including effects of mycorrhizae and exudates on nutrient uptake and assimilation; water transformations and filtration; and weathering of cations and other elements. Thus, the 1D-ICZ model can be used to assess, understand and quantify the complex interactions between the different processes in the soil-plant-water system as well as to provide a tool to design sustainable agricultural management practices by taking under consideration the synergies and trade-offs of the different soil functions. In addition, we have extended the 1D-ICZ to 3D and linked it with the Karst-SWAT model in order to be able to simulate soil functions and the impacts of land management at the watershed scale. The ICZ will simulate the biogeochemistry of each Hydrologic Response Unit (a unit with unique land use, soil type and slope).

Figure 2-2. Schematic of the modified CAST model used in the 1D-ICZ model.

Brief Description of the CLM5-BGC Model – The Community Land Model version 5 (Lawrence et al., 2019) is a deterministic, physics based land-surface model. It is capable of simulating energy and matter fluxes between atmosphere, soil and vegetation, including a functional discretization of the vegetation. It can be forced by atmospheric fields from observations and/or models or coupled directly to an atmospheric model and it modulates the state variables through surface characteristics from remote sensing data. Improvements to its predecessor, CLM4.5, include the spatially variable soil depth, Medlyn stomatal conductance, and irrigation activation by soil moisture thresholds. CLM5 uses over 200 parameters that describe the functionality of the land surface characterization in the model. Those default parameters were calibrated to match a large array of observations across different ecosystem types.

In CLM5-BGC, vegetation is represented conceptually by three different plant C and N pools that are maintained separately for the individual plant organs (leaf, live/dead stem, fine root, live/dead coarse root, and grain). C made available through photosynthesis is first used to support maintenance respiration of live organs based on organ N content, temperature, and a constant base rate. The remaining C can then be allocated to the growth of new tissue considering associated growth respiration costs.

In figure 2-3, we show the land surface discretization into landunit tiles and plant functional types. The area of a grid cell, e.g. representing the footprint Eddy Covariance measurement tower, can consist of a set of plant functional types (e.g. grass combined with broadleaf deciduous forest). Therefore, the simulated energy and matter fluxes can be compared against observations to assess model structure and parametrizations, keeping in mind input data uncertainty and measurement biases. Many evaluation studies in global, regional and site scale have found that CLM5 can successfully model surface fluxes, such as evapotranspiration and gross primary production (see figure 2-4 for a selection of simulated processes in CLM5-BGC). But significant

shortcomings of functional response to environmental changes have also been pointed out, such as vegetation drought response and inter-annual soil moisture variation. Agricultural functional types and management practices are also not yet fully included in CLM5. Recent developments though included bi-annual harvesting and orchard functional types improve the applicability of the model in agriculture. Importantly, CLM5 was not yet comprehensively tested or adapted to reliably simulate karstic landscapes. Functional uncertainty (from parameters and the model itself) and characteristics of landscape as a whole (e.g. added value of mixed forest landscapes to ecosystem resilience) endanger faulty assessments of ecosystem performance, carbon budgets basis in climate change mitigation policies and ecosystem resilience to threats from global change. It is therefore mandatory to increase the understanding of functional response of ecosystems (e.g. through WUE ecosystem function) and make an assessment of its representation in CLM5-BGC.

Figure 2-3. Land surface discretization of CLM5. The model nests different landunit tiles in one grid cell, which are inferred from remote sensing datasets. A landunit consists of nested columns and patches of different soil texture and plant and/or crop functional types (PFT / CFT). The level at which land surface state variables are determined before upscaling to the grid cell depends on the physical representation scale of the variable.

Figure 2-4. Depiction of a selection of included energy fluxes, hydrological and biogeochemical fluxes at the land-surface, PFT and landscape scale in CLM5-BGC.

Application of the models to Zöbelboden - The “LTER Zöbelboden” site (Figure 2-5) is located at the north section of the Kalkalpen National Park of Austria, has a surface area of 90 ha and the coordinates of the station are 47°50'30"N, 14°26'30"E (Hartmann et al., 2011). The site was established by EAA, Environmental Agency Austria in 1992 as a CLRTAP (Convention on Long Range Transboundary Air Pollution) station to monitor a forested ecosystem and it is part of the «eLTER Network (European Long-Term Ecosystem and socio-ecological Research Infrastructure) (Helm et al., 2017). The site is a karstic, mountainous area at 550-956 m a.s.l., <https://deims.org/8eda49e9-1f4e-4f3e-b58e-e0bb25dc32a6>).

The geology of the site is comprised of Triassic dolomite (Hauptdolomit) covered by Jurassic/Cretaceous limestone, Plattenkalk limestones and marls. The topography is characterized by steep slopes of 30-70° and a 60ha plateau. The soils on the slopes are mainly lithic and rendzic leptosols with 12 cm average thickness while the chromic cambisols and hydromorphic stagnosols are found at the plateau with average thickness of 50 cm.

The forest is mainly comprised of beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) and Norway spruce [*Picea abies* (L.) Karst.] that were planted in 1910. Other species found are *Acer pseudoplatanus* L., *Fraxinus excelsior* L., *Larix decidua* Mill. and *Abies alba* Mill.

The following data are being collected at Zöbelboden:

1. Meteorological station and Eddy covariance flux tower
2. Precipitation chemistry
 - Alkalinity ($\mu\text{eq L}^{-1}$)
 - Conductivity (mS m^{-1})
 - pH
 - Ni, Al, Zn, Cu, Pb, Cr, Cd, Mn, Fe, As, Hg ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
 - Ca, Na, Mg, K, Cl, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ (mg L^{-1})
 - NTOT - Total nitrogen (mg L^{-1})
 - DOC - Dissolved Organic Carbon (mgC L^{-1})
3. Soil water chemistry
 - Alkalinity ($\mu\text{eq L}^{-1}$)
 - Conductivity (mS m^{-1})
 - pH
 - Ca, Na, Mg, Cl, K, F, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ (mg L^{-1})
 - NTOT, STOT, DOC (mg L^{-1})
 - TOC, TC - Total Carbon, TIC - Total Inorganic Carbon (%)
4. Throughfall chemistry
 - Alkalinity ($\mu\text{eq L}^{-1}$)
 - Conductivity (mS m^{-1})
 - pH
 - Ca, Na, Mg, Cl, K, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$, $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$, NTOT, DOC (mg L^{-1})
 - Al, As, Ni, Cu, Cr, Cd, Pb, Mn, Fe, Hg, Zn ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)

Figure 2-5. Location and topographic map of the LTER Zöbelboden site.

5. Runoff water chemistry

- Alkalinity ($\mu\text{eq L}^{-1}$)
- Conductivity (mS m^{-1})
- Turbidity (FTU)
- Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- Flow ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)
- Stage (m)
- pH
- Na, Ca, F, K, Cl, Mg, NO_2 , SiO_2 , $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ (mg L^{-1})
- Al, As, Ni, Zn, Cu, Cd, Cr, Mn, Fe, Pb, Sr, Hg ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
- NTOT, STOT, PTOT, TOC, DOC (mg L^{-1})

6. Litterfall chemistry

- Ca, Na, K, Mg (mg g^{-1})
- Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, Mn, B, Mo ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)
- TOC, NTOT, PTOT, STOT (mg g^{-1})

7. Soil structure

- Bulk density (kg m^{-3})
- Soil depth (cm)
- Soil type
- Slope (%)
- Particle size distribution

8. Vegetation
 - Vegetation type
 - Coverage (%)
9. Tree growth
 - Branch growth (kg m^{-2})
 - Foliage growth (kg m^{-2})
 - Stem growth (kg m^{-2})
10. Biomass
 - Aboveground biomass (g m^{-2})
 - Branch biomass (g m^{-2})
 - Foliage biomass (g m^{-2})
 - Stem biomass (g m^{-2})
 - Diameter at breast height (mm)
 - Height for *Fagus sylvatica*, *Picea abies* etc. (m)

The reason that Zöbelboden was chosen as the first site for modeling is because it has been chosen by WP8 as the common site to implement the Whole System Approach.

The Zöbelboden data were used to initialize and calibrate the 1D-ICZ and the CLM5 models and then use the simulation data to:

- assess the impact of drought on the response and resilience of the forested ecosystem, and
- assess how soil structure and soil fertility affects WUE.

Application of the models to Hyytiälä – The second site that was chosen for modeling with the 1D-ICZ was Hyytiälä. The “LTER Hyytiälä” site is located in Southern Finland and it is part of the Station for Measuring Ecosystem-Atmosphere Relationships (SMEAR II). The coordinates of the station are 61°51'N, 24°17'E (180m above sea level). The study site has two mini-catchments (Figure 2-6) that are considered to be independent hydrological units (Pumpanen et al., 2014). The catchments have known borders, with the first catchment (C1) having an area of 889 m² and the second one (C2) having a smaller area of 301 m² (Pumpanen et al., 2014; Peltoniemi et al., 2015).

The geology of the site is comprised of Haplic podzol formed on glacial till with an average thickness of 50-70 cm. The average thickness of the organic layer is 5 cm (Pumpanen et al., 2014). Regarding the vegetation, Hyytiälä SMEAR II LTER site is surrounded by a boreal forest which is dominated by conifers (Kourtchev et al., 2005). More specifically, the most dominant tree species found at the site are the 60year old Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) and the Norwegian pine (*Picea abies* L.) <https://deims.org/663dac80-211d-4c19-a356-04ee0da0f0eb>; Kourtchev et al., 2005). Other species found are *Vaccinium myrtillus* L., *Vaccinium vitis-idaea* L., *Hylocomium splendens* (Hedw.) B.S.G., *Pleurozium schreberi* (Brid.) Mitt., and *Dicranum polysetum* Sw. (Pumpanen et al., 2014).

Figure 2-6. Catchments (C1 and C2) of Hyytiälä SMEAR II LTER site.

The following data are being collected at Hyytiälä:

1. Meteorological station and Eddy covariance flux tower
2. Precipitation chemistry
 - Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)
 - pH
 - $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, P (kg ha^{-1})
 - TC, IC, TOC, TN, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ (mg L^{-1})
 - $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ ($\mu\text{m L}^{-1}$)
3. Soil water chemistry (using lysimeters in soil pits)
 - Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)
 - pH
 - TC, IC, TOC, TN, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ (mg L^{-1})
 - $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ ($\mu\text{m L}^{-1}$)
4. Runoff water chemistry (through weirs)
 - Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)
 - pH
 - TC, IC, TOC, TN, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ (mg L^{-1})
 - $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ ($\mu\text{m L}^{-1}$)

5. Throughfall chemistry
 - $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, P (kg ha^{-1})
6. Soil structure
 - Bulk density (g cm^{-3})
 - Soil depth (cm)
 - Soil type
 - Slope (%)
 - Particle size distribution
7. Litterfall
 - Aboveground litterfall (kg m^{-2})
 - Leaf N and C content (%)
8. Vegetation
 - Vegetation type
 - Coverage (%)
9. Tree growth and biomass
 - Aboveground biomass (kg m^{-2})
 - Aboveground growth of trees (kg m^{-2})
 - LAI

The Hyytiälä data were used to initialize and calibrate the 1D-ICZ and the CLM5 models and then use the simulation data to assess the impact of drought on the response and resilience of the forested ecosystem.

Application of the models to Svartberget – The third site that was chosen for modeling with 1D-ICZ is Svartberget (270 m above sea level). The Svartberget site consists of a boreal forest and is located at the heart of Krycklan Catchment Study (KCS) area (Figure 2-7), <https://www.icos-sweden.se/Svartberget>. KCS is located about 50 km northwest of Umeå in Northern Sweden and has coordinates 64°140' N, 19° 460' E (Laudon et al., 2021).

The geology is dominated by paragneiss i.e. Svecofennian metasediments/metagraywacke with acid and intermediate metavolcanic rocks and, basic metavolcanic rocks (Laudon et al., 2013; Laudon et al., 2021). However, during the last deglaciation the area was divided into two separate regions. Quaternary deposits at higher altitudes are dominated by till (iron podzols) and peat while quaternary deposits at lower altitudes are dominated by postglacial sediments (Laudon et al., 2013).

Regarding the vegetation, the most dominant species of the boreal forest are Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) (63%) and Norwegian pine (*Picea abies*) (26%). Other species found are *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *Hylocomium splendens*, *Pleurozium schreberi*, *Sphagnum* spp. along with sedges and dwarf shrubs (Laudon et al., 2021).

Figure 2-7. Krycklan Catchment Study a) sub-catchments and tree density, b) stream network, c) quaternary deposits, d) central area.

The following data are being collected at Svartberget:

1. Meteorological station and Eddy covariance flux tower
2. Precipitation chemistry
 - NO₃-N, NH₄-N, P (kg ha⁻¹)
3. Stream chemistry
 - Conductivity (mS m⁻¹)
 - pH
 - Br, Ca, Na, Mg, K, Cl, F, P, NO₃-N, PO₄-P, SO₄-S (mg L⁻¹)
 - TOC, DOC (mg L⁻¹)
4. Groundwater chemistry
 - Br, Ca, Na, Mg, K, Cl, F, NO₃-N, PO₄-P, SO₄-S (mg L⁻¹)
 - TOC, DOC (mg L⁻¹)

2.3. WUE modelling with watershed scale models

The objective here is to scale up and assess ecosystems at the watershed level. In addition to the above, we would need **hydrologic data and river and groundwater chemistry data**. We will use two models; SWAT and INCA.

Brief Description of the SWAT Model – SWAT is a deterministic, continuous time (daily time step) basin scale model that was designed to simulate the hydrology, sediment yield and water quality (nutrient and pesticides) of ungauged watersheds (Arnold et al., 1998) and evaluate the impact of agricultural management practices on water quality and agricultural yields. The watershed is first subdivided into subcatchments and each subcatchment into hydrologic response units (HRU) that are a function of soil type, land use and land slope. The model has incorporated the following components: weather generator routine, hydrologic mass balance, soil temperature and soil properties, plant growth, nutrients, pesticides, bacteria and pathogen mass balances, and land management practices. The hydrologic component of each HRU includes the following processes: evapotranspiration, plant uptake, surface runoff and infiltration (using the modified Curve Number or the Green-Ampt method), percolation, lateral subsurface flow, groundwater return flow from the shallow aquifer, deep aquifer losses and channel transmission loss subroutines. Water balance is conducted for the snow compartment, soil, shallow aquifer and deep aquifer. Plant growth is based on the EPIC crop model and uses the "heat units" concept which relates crop growth to the excess of daily temperature above a base temperature. Potential evapotranspiration, leaf area index, rooting depth and soil water content determine the water uptake of plants.

SWAT calculates actual evapotranspiration using the Penman-Montheith equation and adjusts it based on the water balance. Precipitation and temperature are being adjusted based on their lapse rate and the model uses two compensation factors EPCO (Plant evaporation compensation factor) and ESCO (Soil evaporation compensation factor) as calibration parameters to achieve hydrologic mass balance. At the same time, it calculates the plant biomass for each HRU/land use-soil-slope combination. Plant growth is based on heat units and the scheduling of growth for different plant types. The model calculates potential plant growth as a function of the Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) intercepted times the Radiation Use Efficiency (RUE). The intercepted PAR is estimated using the total PAR, the light extinction coefficient of the plant and the Leaf Area Index (LAI). On the other hand, RUE is adjusted by the atmospheric CO₂ and the vapor pressure deficit. Water uptake by plants is estimated using the maximum PET, root depth and root density in the different layers in the soil. The actual water uptake is calculated using the EPCO compensation factor that adjusts the water potential to actual water uptake. The actual plant growth is estimated from the potential growth adjusting it for water stress, temperature stress and nutrient stress. The actual biomass growth divided by the actual ET is the plant WUE.

The SWAT model was modified to account for karstic geomorphological settings "Karst-SWAT" (Nikolaidis et al., 2013; Nerantzaki et al., 2015). The modified model was conceptualized and developed using geomorphological data and knowledge of the hydrologic processes occurring at the Koiliaris CZO. One key characteristic of the Karst model is that it can account for the water that originates outside the hydrologic basin of Koiliaris CZO, the extended karst, as well as for the water quality and sediment transport within the karst by assuming two well mixed reservoirs that account for the varying hydraulic conductivities of the upper and lower karst. The Karst-SWAT model after being verified at the CZO was scaled-up to simulate the Region of Crete and assess the regional hydrologic budget (Malagò et al., 2016) as well as the impacts of climate change to the region (Nerantzaki et al., 2019).

Koiliaris CZO (www.koiliaris-czo.tuc.gr) is one of the European CZOs that is typical for the Mediterranean karstic environment with soils under imminent threat of desertification (e.g. soil carbon loss) due to climate change and the clearing of forests and natural vegetation for cropping

and livestock grazing and represents human impacts over the centuries (Nikolaidis, 2011; Moraetis et al., 2012). De-vegetation and inappropriate cultivation practices induces soil organic matter losses making soils susceptible to erosion and desertification with global consequences for food security, climate change, biodiversity, water quality, and agricultural economy. The Karst-SWAT model was used to simulate the WUE and assess the impact of droughts on WUE.

Brief Description of the INCA Model

The INCA-N (Integrated Catchments model for Nitrogen) is a dynamic, daily time step model for catchment-scale simulation of nitrogen fluxes and transformations with a focus on soil and surface water processes (Whitehead et al., 1998; Wade et al. 2002a). The model simulates terrestrial and aquatic hydrology and biogeochemistry based on daily time step mass balances. The following datasets are required to run the model:

- Catchment and sub-catchment properties including land cover, length of the main stream channel and connectivity between sub-catchments.
- Daily time series of air temperature and precipitation
- Estimates of atmospheric N deposition
- Measurements of flow and nitrogen species at one or more points in the river network for model calibration.

The INCA landscape representation consists of a stream network flowing through one or more subcatchments (Figure 2-8). Within each subcatchment, there can be one or more land cover types. All biogeochemical processes are simulated for each land cover type in each sub-catchment using the principle of a generic “cell”.

Figure 2-8. Generic INCA landscape representation. A river catchment (Level 1) is divided into one or more subcatchments (Level 2). Each subcatchment is comprised of a river reach and one or more land cover types. All calculations are performed at a generic “cell” level. From Wade et al. (2002b).

INCA simulates both terrestrial and in-stream hydrology. In each generic “cell”, land phase hydrology is simulated using three vertically stacked boxes (Figure 2-9) representing direct runoff, soilwater and groundwater. Water from each of these boxes has a unique chemical signal and can contribute to streamflow. Precipitation and snowmelt enter the direct runoff and soilwater boxes. All evapotranspiration is assumed to occur from the soilwater box. Saturation excess runoff is generated from the soilwater box. Infiltration excess runoff occurs when the infiltration capacity of the soilwater box is exceeded.

Figure 2-9. Conceptual diagram of water stores and fluxes used in the terrestrial hydrology component of the model.

Instream hydrology is simulated based on flow velocities estimated from Manning’s equation. The model is able to simulate either “main stem” or branching river networks.

INCA-N simulates pools and fluxes of ammonium, nitrate and dissolved organic nitrogen (DON). Nitrate and ammonia are added to the system through atmospheric deposition. The model can be calibrated against observed time series of flow, ammonia, nitrate and DON. The model can be calibrated against a range of performance statistics including the Pearson correlation coefficient (R^2), Nash-Sutcliffe (NS) and Kling-Gupta (KGE) statistics.

Key nitrogen transformation processes (Figure 2-10) in the model include:

- Sorption and desorption of organic nitrogen from the solid phase (i.e., production of DON)
- Mineralisation of DON to ammonia
- Immobilisation of ammonia to DON
- Nitrification of ammonia
- Fixation of ammonia from the atmosphere
- Denitrification of nitrate

Figure 2-10. Nitrogen pools and processes simulated by the model.

Immobilisation of ammonia and plant uptake of inorganic nitrogen are the main biological removal mechanisms in the model. Immobilisation rates are dependent on soil temperature and soil moisture status (i.e., rates proceed more quickly in warmer and/or wetter soils). Plant uptake of ammonia and nitrate is simulated as a loss process in the model. Plants remove nitrate and ammonia from the soilwater box at a rate proportional to actual evapotranspiration (AET). This ensures that uptake only occurs during the growing season. Removal rates are dependent on concentration in the soilwater box a Michaelis-Menten type relationship defined by an uptake rate and half-saturation concentrations for ammonium and nitrate respectively.

Land phase chemistry is calculated separately for each land cover type in each subcatchment. All land-phase nitrogen process and transformation rates are dependent on soil moisture deficit and soil temperature. Land phase hydrology and chemistry equations are solved simultaneously. Mass fluxes of nitrogen from each subcatchment are transferred to the relevant stream reach once a day.

Instream nitrogen processes include nitrification and denitrification. Denitrification can also occur in groundwater.

3. Results

3.1. Time series analysis results

Flux tower, meteorological, precipitation and soil moisture data from 11 sites (Hyytiälä, Brasschaat, Rollesbroich, Selhausen, Wüstebach, Renon, Collelongo, Zöbelboden, Svartberget, Koiliaris and Yatir) were used at this phase for the time series analysis. Figure 3-1 presents a comparison of the monthly GPP time series, Figure 3-2 the ET time series and Figure 3-3, the PDSI time series for the 11 sites.

Figure 3-1. Monthly GPP time series for the 11 studied sites.

Figure 3-2. Monthly ET time series for the 11 studied sites.

Figure 3-3. Normalized PDSI time series for the 11 studied sites.

Figure 3-4. Comparison of WUE with PDSI time series for the 11 studied sites.

Drought analysis using the Flux Tower and Precipitation data – The monthly GPP, ET and WUE flux tower data along with the PDSI were used to determine drought response and resilience indices for each site for all drought periods. Table 3-1 presents the determination of the drought indices for the 25 extreme drought events realized at the 10 forested stations. The number of consecutive months with PDSI below -2 range from 2 in Brasschaat to 29 in Yatir while the average PDSI during these periods ranged from -2.0 at Zobelboden to -3.16 at Renon. The Drought Index ranged from -4.36 to -81.78, however only 4 events had values less than -40 across all sites. The GPP Response Index ranged from 676 g m⁻² y⁻¹ at Yatir to 2243 g m⁻² y⁻¹ at Wusterbach. Only the two events at Yatir had an annual growth less than 900 g m⁻². The resilience Index ranged from 0.58 to 1.0, while for 22 out of the 25 events the index was higher than 0.7 meaning that it reached 70% of the non-drought maximum growth.

Table 3-1. Determination of drought indices for 10 forested station using flux tower data

eLTER Site	No of months with PDSI < -2	Average PDSI	Drought Index	Response index	GPP max	Resilience Index
Hyytiala	17	-2.13	-36.21	998.88	8.44	0.81
	7	-2.46	-17.22	1108.99	8.09	0.77
	21	-3.14	-65.94	1007.10	7.41	0.71
	3	-2.73	-8.19	1044.51	7.35	0.70
Renon	7	-3.16	-22.12	1168.91	7.14	0.61
	15	-2.47	-37.05	1409.51	8.45	0.73
	16	-2.2	-35.2	1593.83	11.64	1.00
	6	-2.32	-13.92	1625.47	9.07	0.78
Collelongo	21	-2.49	-52.29	1028.69	8.22	0.57
	8	-2.31	-18.48	1210.58	10.46	0.73
	8	-2.67	-21.36	1557.94	10.39	0.73
Yatir	29	-2.82	-81.78	676.16	4.31	0.75
	9	-2.29	-20.61	775.32	4.30	0.74
Brasschaat	28	-2.07	-57.96	1319.48	7.94	0.58
	9	-2.28	-20.52	1696.95	10.57	0.77
	2	-2.18	-4.36	1725.84	13.65	1.00
Selhausen	5	-2.76	-13.8	1088.61	12.83	0.79
	4	-3.11	-12.44	953.26	11.2	0.69
Rollesbroich	12	-2.22	-26.64	1604.78	8.75	0.77
	10	-2.3	-23	1816.48	11.39	1.00
Wusterbach	9	-2.17	-19.53	1415.59	9.11	0.70
	7	-2.3	-16.1	2243.53	12.63	0.97
Zobelboden	5	-2.3	-11.5	1113.4	8.5	0.91
	7	-2	-14	1120.3	9.25	0.99
Svartberget	7	-2.31	-16.17	1152.18	8.65	1.00
Hyytiala	17	-2.13	-36.21	998.88	8.44	0.81
	7	-2.46	-17.22	1108.99	8.09	0.77
	21	-3.14	-65.94	1007.10	7.41	0.71
	3	-2.73	-8.19	1044.51	7.35	0.70

Figures 3-5 through 3-8 present a comparison of the Drought Index with GPP Response Index for all the drought events (Figure 3-5), for Northern Europe events (Figure 3-6), for Central European events (Figure 3-7) and for Mediterranean events (Figure 3-8). The GPP Response is decreasing as the Drought duration and intensity are increasing. This can be observed both at the European level (including all the events together) as well as at the regional levels. However, it should be noted that for the low drought index events we have a high variability of the GPP response. On the other hand, we do not observe any significant trends in the impact of the intensity of drought on the Resilience of the system to reach maximum growth for Europe as a whole. It appears that all forested ecosystems are quite resilient to drought events regardless of the location.

It is important to mention at this point that the EC-GPP fluxes of Zöbelboden (not measured but derived from the EC measurements using flux partitioning) are not derived with the same methodology as the other sites that follow the ICOS methodology. The EC-GPP fluxes are responding to the short-term and average monthly dynamics, because the GPP model is being fitted to each month using data from all years. This means that the EC-GPP fluxes aren't suitable for analysis looking at drought response and recovery. For this, we would need to parameterize for each month of each year, or be even more resolved than this, which most sites could do but for the Zöbelboden site this wasn't possible due to low levels of data retention. With such parameterization in time, one can implicitly derive legacy effects of drought. However, in a certain analysis that was conducted by the Environment Agency of Austria, such dynamics cannot be seen, and if they were seen it is simply to coincidence with the driving weather variables R_g and VPD. Despite these concerns, it was chosen to keep these two datapoint in the analysis because the results were consistent with the response of other sites in central Europe. In addition, the Drought Index values were low (less than -25) and did not affect the trend analysis. On the other hand, the GPP estimates can be used for the calibration of the models for the Zöbelboden site.

Figure 3-5. Comparison of the Drought Index with a) GPP Response Index and b) Resilience for all the sites and drought events.

Figure 3-6. Comparison of Drought Index with GPP Response Index for Hyytiälä drought events.

Figure 3-7. Comparison of the Drought Index with a) GPP Response Index and b) Resilience for the stations in Central Europe drought events.

Figure 3-8. Comparison of Drought Index with GPP Response Index for the stations in Mediterranean drought events.

3.2. WUE modelling with 1D models

Simulation of Zöbelboden using the 1D-ICZ model

The Zöbelboden site has flux tower data for CO₂ and latent heat fluxes from 2014 to 2020. For this site, we used 2015-2019 data to calibrate the model and 1996-2020 to simulate the site and estimate the Water Use Efficiency that will be assessed for the impacts of droughts.

Initialization of the 1D-ICZ model – The model is driven by monthly time series input of precipitation, ET, Temperature, Photosynthetic Active Radiation (PAR) and nutrient inputs from atmospheric deposition. All the necessary data (Table 3-2) for the simulation were retrieved from the eLTER Repository (DEIMS-SDR, Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry). The input time series of precipitation were calculated by summing up daily values and converting them from mm to m. The input time series of temperature were estimated by taking the monthly average from daily data. The input time series of ET (Figure 3-17) were estimated using the Penman-Monteith equation and compared against the latent heat flux measurement. The parameters of the equation (r_a and r_s) were adjusted so the ET estimates to be as close to the cumulative latent heat flux measurements as possible. In this way, we used the Penman-Monteith equation to estimate the ET for the 1996-2020 period of available data. The input time series of PAR were calculated by eliminating all zeros and by taking the monthly average of the remaining half-hourly data. Regarding the nutrient inputs, we used soil chemistry initial conditions for Ca, Mg, Na, K, H⁺, F, NO₃N, NH₄N and precipitation chemistry monthly data for Ca, Mg, Na, K, H⁺, Al, SO₄S, NO₃N and NH₄N.

Table 3-2. Input parameters for each 1D-ICZ sub-model using data from eLTER Repository

Parameter name and description	Timestep	Units	Model
Precipitation	Monthly	m	HYDRUS-1D
Evapotranspiration	Monthly	m	HYDRUS-1D
Air temperature	Monthly	°C	HYDRUS-1D PROSUM
Bulk density	-	g cm ⁻³	HYDRUS-1D
	-	kg m ⁻³	CAST
Soil chemistry: Ca, Mg, Na, K, H ⁺ , F, NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺	Initial (month)	mol L ⁻¹	Excel Tool for HYDRUS-1D
Precipitation chemistry: Ca, Mg, Na, K, H ⁺ , Al, SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺	Monthly	mol L ⁻¹	Excel Tool for HYDRUS-1D
Clay content (for each layer)	-	%	CAST
Silt-clay content (for each layer)	-	%	CAST
PAR (photosynthetic active radiation)	Monthly	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	PROSUM

Calibration of the 1D-ICZ model – Firstly, we calibrated the 1D-ICZ model using the flux tower data for the period 2015-2019 and then we used the calibrated parameters to simulate period 1996-2020 for drought analysis. Our primary goal was to calibrate the PROSUM sub-model (plant model), meaning the GPP using flux tower measurements. Doing so, we were able to simulate the limiting factors of growth, the nutrient uptake and also, the C and N stocks for the leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. For the CAST sub-model we only used TOC measurements in order to simulate SOC as we didn't have available Water Stable Aggregate (WSA) fractionation data to properly simulate the soil formation and structure. Then, we calibrated geochemistry (Ca, F, K, Mg, Na, NH₄N, NO₃N, H⁺, SO₄S) for the period of time 2015-2019 using soil water chemistry data for the

first soil layer (0-10cm). In addition, we used runoff water chemistry data in order to calibrate the same soil chemistry components for the last soil layer (4th layer, 30-40cm). The soil profile was defined to be at 40cm with five nodes and four layers (10cm for each layer). No forest management except the removal of bark beetle infested trees (e.g. harvest, tillage, addition of fertilizers, compost or manure) has been applied at Zöbelboden since 1992.

The data discussed previously were used to initialize and calibrate the 1D-ICZ model. After the model was calibrated, the model parameters were used to simulate the 25-year period (1996-2020) in order to 1) study the impact of drought on the response and resilience of the forested ecosystem and 2) assess how soil structure and fertility affects WUE. In the latter case, the goal was achieved by performing a scenario of addition of organic matter (compost) via sub-model CAST.

Results – Zöbelboden 1D-ICZ

The 1D-ICZ model successfully simulated the GPP of the Zöbelboden forested ecosystem along with the growth limitations, the total C and N biomass, the nutrient uptake, the C and N stocks of leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. Figure 3-9 compares the monthly GPP flux measurements and the simulated GPP by 1D-ICZ over time. Figure 3-10 presents a) the comparison of annual measured and simulated GPP, and b) a comparison of the cumulative annual measured and simulated GPP over time. The RMSE between the monthly simulated and field data was 80.12 gC m⁻² while the annual RMSE was 247.55 gC m⁻² (or 22% of the mean annual GPP). Finally, the difference between the cumulative field and modelled GPP was 3,302.33 gC m⁻² which corresponds to 10% closure. These results suggest that the 1D-ICZ model is capable of simulating GPP while accounting correctly for the limiting factors, the nutrient fluxes, temperature and PAR.

Figure 11 presents the evolution of the limiting factors to growth and Figure 3-12 shows the evolution of total biomass of C and N over time (1996-2020). The total biomass of C increases during the years 1996-2011 and then slightly decreases during the years 2012-2020. On the contrary, the total biomass of N remains stable. Regarding the nutrient uptake, figure 3-13 shows that the utilization trend of N follows the utilization trend of C and that Mg uptake < Ca uptake < K uptake < P uptake. Figures 3-14 and 3-15 illustrate the C and N stocks of leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. Overall, C and N stocks of leaf, root and mycorrhizae fluctuate over time. In contrast, C and N stocks of wood increase and then stabilize. The average C and N stocks of leaf are 16.5 mol m⁻² and 0.20 mol m⁻² respectively. The average C and N stocks of wood are 136 mol m⁻² and 0.47 mol m⁻² respectively. The average C and N stock of root is 26.5 mol m⁻² and 0.20 mol m⁻² respectively. Lastly, the average C stock of mycorrhizae is 14.4 mol m⁻².

In order to calibrate the model, the following changes in the input had to be performed. Since there were no available deposition P measurements, P concentrations used as boundary conditions in the PROSUM sub-model were adjusted to overcome P limitation to growth since P was the most significant limiting factor. Adjustment of the P input was not enough to fully calibrate plant growth during the first seven years of the longterm simulation. It was observed that nutrient (Al, Ca, K, Mg, Na, NH₄N, NO₃N) monthly measurements in the precipitation during the first seven years were significantly lower than those of the rest of the period and that was the reason of the deviation in the GPP between model and field data. To overcome this problem, we replaced the nutrient fluxes of the first seven years with the monthly nutrient measurements of the next seven years. To fine tune the GPP simulation, the parameters associated with temperature and PAR were also calibrated.

Figures 3-16 and 3-17 present the monthly simulated GPP and ET values for 1996-2020. The data will then be used to estimate the WUE for Zöbelboden and for the drought analysis. The peak monthly GPP ranged from 160 gC m⁻² to 450 gC m⁻² with an average peak of about 250 gC m⁻² month⁻¹. The ET was estimated using the Penman-Monteith equation and calibrated against the flux tower latent heat data by adjusting the atmospheric and soil resistance parameters.

Figure 3-9. Comparison of simulated monthly GPP with flux tower data (2014-2020).

Figure 3-10. Comparison of a) simulated annual GPP with GPP flux measurements and b) cumulative annual values of simulated versus field data.

Figure 3-11. Evolution of limiting factors to growth.

Figure 3-12. Total C and N biomass with time.

Figure 3-13. Simulated nutrient uptake with time.

Figure 3-14. Simulated C stock for the leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae.

Figure 3-15. Simulated N stock for the leaf, wood and root.

Figure 3-16. Simulated GPP for the period 1996-2020.

Figure 3-17. Simulated ET for the period 1996-2020.

Geochemistry

Figures 3-18 to 3-35 present a comparison of solute (Ca, F, K, Mg, Na, NH₄N, NO₃N, H⁺, SO₄S) measurements versus the simulated solute concentrations for the first (0-10cm) and the fourth soil layer (30-40cm) of the model. The 1D-ICZ model was able to simulate the solute transport of F, K, Na, NH₄N, NO₃N and SO₄S quite well while for the simulations of Ca, Mg and H⁺ the model was over or under predicting. Deposition data were available for Ca, K, Mg, Na, NH₄N, NO₃N, H⁺, and SO₄S but not for F. It was assumed that F originates entirely from precipitation, and thus the input values for boundary conditions were set to be the same order of magnitude as the soil measurements. The reason why solutes Ca and Mg couldn't be simultaneously simulated properly has to do with the weathering formulation of the model. The sub-model SAFE that simulates weathering processes includes six minerals in which one of them is dolomite and it does not include one of the primary minerals of Zöbelboden geology, limestone. If limestone was to be added in the model, the weathering of dolomite would simulate Mg concentrations and then the weathering of limestone would provide the additional Ca needed for the simulation of Ca. This will also correct the pH simulation. In the near future, we intend to modify the code of sub-model SAFE and the process of limestone weathering.

Figure 3-18. Comparison of Ca measurements with simulated Ca for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-19. Comparison of Ca measurements with simulated Ca for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-20. Comparison of F measurements with simulated Ca for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-21. Comparison of F measurements with simulated F for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-22. Comparison of K measurements with simulated K for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-23. Comparison of K measurements with simulated K for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-24. Comparison of Mg measurements with simulated Mg for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-25. Comparison of Mg measurements with simulated Mg for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-26. Comparison of Na measurements with simulated Na for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-27. Comparison of Na measurements with simulated Na for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-28. Comparison of NH_4N measurements with simulated NH_4N for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-29. Comparison of NH_4N measurements with simulated NH_4N for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-30. Comparison of NO_3N measurements with simulated NO_3N for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-31. Comparison of NO_3N measurements with simulated NO_3N for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-32. Comparison of H⁺ measurements with simulated H⁺ for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-33. Comparison of H⁺ measurements with simulated H⁺ for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-34. Comparison of SO₄S measurements with simulated SO₄S for the 1st soil layer (0-10cm) over time (2015-2019).

Figure 3-35. Comparison of SO_4S measurements with simulated SO_4S for the 4th soil layer (30-40cm) over time (2015-2019).

Soil formation and structure

Figure 3-36 shows the SOC of each soil layer during the period 1996-2020. Figures 3-37 to 3-39 presents the OC content in silt-clay sized microaggregates (AC1), microaggregates (AC2) and macroaggregates (AC3) respectively. Finally, Figures 3-40 to 3-42 present the evolution of WSA mass contained in silt-clay sized microaggregates ($<53\mu\text{m}$), microaggregates ($53\text{-}250\mu\text{m}$) and macroaggregates ($>250\mu\text{m}$). Since there were no available WSA fractionation data in order to properly calibrate the CAST sub-model and thus, simulate the soil formation (aggregation and disaggregation) and soil structure, TOC measurements were used to partially calibrate the CAST sub-model for the first soil layer (0-10cm). The results suggest that the SOC of each soil layer decreases over time (Figure 3-36). This is due to the fact that no carbon addition is taking place and the system's internal carbon circulation alone is not sufficient to maintain and/or increase carbon storage. The OC contained in aggregate fractions AC1 and AC3 appear to be relatively stable and the OC contained in AC2 appears to be reducing over time. Finally, the WSA mass in AC1, AC2 and AC3 remain relatively constant with time with small increases in the macroaggregate content (AC3). The simulation of the carbon cycle can be improved by incorporating soil fractionation data from the site.

Figure 3-36. SOC for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-37. Organic carbon contained in silt-clay sized microaggregates (<53 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-38. Organic carbon contained in microaggregates (53-250 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-39. Organic carbon contained in macroaggregates (>250 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-40. Mass of WSA in silt-clay sized microaggregates (<53 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-41. Mass of WSA in microaggregates (53-250 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-42. Mass of WSA in macroaggregates (>250 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

WUE and impact of drought analysis:

The WUE was estimated by using the simulated GPP and ET over the simulated period 1996-2020. Figure 3-43 shows the monthly simulated WUE in kg m^{-3} and figure 3-44 presents the annual average WUE over the years. In the figure, one can observe that one monthly value of WUE was extremely high (21.05 kg m^{-3}). This value was high due to a very low ET for that month and it was eliminated from the analysis. Overall, WUE varies between 1.95 to 5.45 kg m^{-3} and has an annual average of 3.67 kg m^{-3} .

Drought analysis was conducted using Palmer's Drought Severity Index (PDSI). PDSI was calculated for the period 1996-2020 (Figure 3-45). Drought impact to plant growth was assessed by estimating the Drought Index, the GPP Response Index and the Resilience Index for the extreme drought events ($\text{PDSI} < -2.0$) during the 25-year simulation period. Figure 3-46 shows the comparison of the Drought Index to the GPP Response Index and Figure 3-47 presents the comparison of the Drought Index to the Drought Resilience Index.

During the drought analysis, extreme events of drought were observed:

- From December 2000 to May 2001
- From August 2003 to April 2004
- From December 2010 to November 2011
- From August 2015 to December 2015, and
- From May 2018 to November 2018

The results show that drought is directly impacting GPP and in particular the GPP response and resilience in a positive way. More precisely, when the severity of drought increases so does the response and so does the resilience. These relationships are quite strong and the R^2 for the Drought versus GPP Response Index is 0.73 and for the Resilience Index 0.67. These results suggest that the forested ecosystem of Zöbelboden is responding in a positive way to extreme drought events and the ecosystem is resilient. At Zöbelboden, major drought impacts on tree growth occur when it coincides with the main growing period which is May-June. Might be one reason for an eventual low response or even a positive response after the year 2015. From tree growth data, a low but significant decrease during years of drought (2003, 2011, 2015) and one year after drought when comparing with wet years have been observed.

Figure 3-43. Simulated monthly WUE for the period 1996-2020.

Figure 3-44. Annual average WUE evolution with time.

Figure 3-45. Simulated monthly PDSI for the period 1996-2020.

Figure 3-46. Comparison of Drought Index to the GPP Response Index for Zöbelboden.

Figure 3-47. Comparison of Drought Index to the Drought Resilience Index for Zöbelboden.

Impact of organic matter addition:

A scenario of addition of organic matter (compost) was performed in order to assess the impact of soil structure and fertility to WUE. According to the 1D-ICZ model, the litterfall varies between 6.1 and 14.6 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ and has an average value of 9.6 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹. So, for this scenario the addition of 10 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ that is evenly distributed during the months between October to January (2.5 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) was selected. The additional SOM was added in the form of compost.

Figure 3-48 presents the SOC of each soil layer after the SOM addition. With the addition of 10 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, SOC of the first layer increases from 70 tC ha⁻¹ to 109 tC ha⁻¹ over the 25 year period. Approximately 39 t ha⁻¹ were sequestered in the top soil layer out of the 250 tC ha⁻¹ added during the 25 years. Figures 3-49 to 3-51 present the amount of fixed OC in AC1, AC2 and AC3 after the SOM addition. From these figures one can observe that the sum of fixed OC in AC1, AC2, AC3 isn't equal to SOC. That happens because SOC involves the OC in aggregates (AC1, AC2, AC3), the fresh organic matter (DPM, RPM) and the dissolved SOC (BIO, HUM). With those being said, it seems that the OC is not incorporated as the coarse organic matter isn't fragmented to fine

organic matter. Figures 3-52 to 3-54 illustrate the WSA mass in silt-clay sized microaggregates (<53 μm), microaggregates (53-250 μm) and macroaggregates (>250 μm) after SOM addition. Figures 3-55 and 3-56 illustrate the evolution of porosity of each soil layer before and after SOM addition. Similarly, Figures 3-57 and 3-58 present the evolution of bulk density before and after SOM addition. Both porosity and bulk density decrease over time after SOM addition.

The results illustrate how SOM addition improves soil structure and soil dynamics by increasing the amount of carbon sequestered in the upper soil layer, the WSA content and by decreasing the bulk density of the soil and the porosity which in turn increases the water holding capacity of the soil.

Figure 3-48. SOC after organic matter addition for the period of time 1996-2020.

Figure 3-49. Fixed OC in silt-clay sized microaggregates (<53 μm) after the compost addition.

Figure 3-50. Fixed OC in microaggregates (53-250 μm) after the compost addition.

Figure 3-51. Fixed OC in macroaggregates (>250 μm) after the compost addition.

Figure 3-52. WSA mass in silt-clay sized microaggregates (AC1) after compost addition.

Figure 3-53. WSA mass in microaggregates (AC2) after compost addition.

Figure 3-54. WSA mass in macroaggregates (AC3) after compost addition.

Figure 3-55. Porosity of each soil layer over time before SOM addition.

Figure 3-56. Porosity of each soil layer after SOM addition.

Figure 3-57. Bulk density of each soil layer over time before SOM addition.

Figure 3-58. Bulk density of each soil layer after SOM addition.

Simulation of Zöbelboden using the CLM5-BGC model

Set-up of the Zöbelboden site CLM5-BGC

We set-up the CLM5 model with the biogeochemistry module turned on, so that the vertical cycling of carbon and nitrogen is modelled. We used the coordinates of the Eddy Covariance (EC) tower as input to default scripts of the CLM5 Repository (Lawrence et al., 2019) to create a domain file with coordinate information on the site and a surface file with information on the soil and surface characterizations. Information on soil structure is taken from the Harmonized World Soil Database and information on land cover and land use as well as vegetation functional types are taken from several remote sensing products including MODIS. This is checked to match the actual land cover of the EC footprint indicated by the metadata site information and adapted if it does not match. We conducted the modelling using default, literature review based parameters and other default input data are taken from the CLM5 repository. The atmospheric forcing (temperature, precipitation, incoming radiation, relative humidity, wind speed and atmospheric pressure) driving the model came from the COSMO reanalysis 6 (Bollmeyer et al., 2015), in 6 km space resolution and 6-hourly time resolution from 1995 to 2018. The soil and vegetation carbon pool equilibrium states of the boundary condition at the start of the production runs are determined by a long-term (~1500 years) spin-up simulation starting from arbitrary conditions until equilibrium carbon pool size and exchange rates are reached. The simulation time resolution is half-hourly but the output frequency is set to daily.

Results – Zöbelboden CLM5-BGC

We extracted the evapotranspiration (ET) time series of the CLM5-production run for Zöbelboden and show the time series together with the correspondent in-situ time-series in Figure 3-59. The time range (1996–2018) was set by the earliest available in-situ observation and the end of the available forcing data. Importantly, CLM5-BGC includes negative ET values (condensation). For the comparison, just data are included that are present in both in-situ and CLM5-BGC datasets. The daily ET (in mm s^{-1}) outputs of CLM5-BGC were resampled to match the in-situ data used above (mm month^{-1}).

While the variability is well represented (coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.80$), clear systematic overestimations are evident during the summer seasons (peaks) and underestimations during and winter seasons (troughs). As a result, the root mean square error RMSE amounts to considerable $18.92 \text{ mm month}^{-1}$. In the years 2013 and 2014 the simulated summer ET peaks compared good to observations; but these were exceptions. This shows a good representation of inter-seasonal variability (through high R^2), which is also visible in well agreeing spring and autumn transitions. But the amplitude of change between maximum / summer and minimum / winter ET is much higher in the simulations than observed. This could be related to a specific set of vegetation parameters dealing with seasonal vegetation response in CLM5. Further research will investigate the difference between bias of simulated soil evaporation and transpiration seasonal amplitude to the observations. Further analysis. e.g. on the uncertainty of ecosystem (vegetation and soil) parameterization should focus on improving, i.e. decreasing the seasonal amplitude of ecosystem ET in Zöbelboden.

Figure 3-59. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) ET (in mm month^{-1}). Data for this site and variable was available from 1996 until 2018.

We compared the simulated gross primary production (GPP) time series at the Zöbelboden site with the in-situ observations (Figure 3-60). The GPP data was available from 2014 (the start of the available GPP in-situ data) to 2018 (end of the forcing data for CLM5-BGC). Simulated and observed GPP time series were resampled to monthly sums (gC month^{-1}) and the analysis will just consider the time period where both, in-situ and simulation data were available.

The general variability is well represented again in simulations, reaching a high R^2 of 0.89 with the in-situ observations. Opposite to the ET comparison, GPP in summer is underestimated by the simulations. During winter, there is just a slight overestimation by the simulations compared to the in-situ measured GPP (total $\text{RMSE} = 35.5$). Especially the GPP magnitude of late winters, in 2017 and 2018 is well represented in CLM5-BGC outputs. In 2018 the summer GPP bias is closer to the observations than in other years. But the systematic summer GPP underestimation combined with the overestimation of ET gives further clues on missed functional response of vegetation, so that parameters that influence the vegetation transpiration per assimilated carbon or leaf area should be scrutinized thoroughly. Possibly the overestimation of summer ET is then rather related to a

systematic overestimation of soil evaporation. This needs to be investigated further, but more prominent partitioned evapotranspiration (soil evaporation and transpiration parts) is required. Also, the limited amount of GPP years limits the confidence in these conclusions. Station PI's and global, continental and national station networks are encouraged to promote more consistent long-term (>10 years) measurement projects to have a better basis for confident analysis on ecosystem functional variability.

Figure 3-60. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) GPP (in g C month⁻¹). Data for this site and variable was available from 2014 until 2018.

We used the GPP and ET time series from in-situ and CLM5-BGC simulations described above to calculate the water use efficiency (Figure 3-61). The time range for WUE is therefore limited by the earliest available data between GPP and ET and the first end date between the two (2014-2018 for Zöbelboden). We masked negative values of the ET and GPP time series (only relevant for simulated ET which contains negative values for condensation), to not have physically pointless negative WUE values. Further, minimal and zero values in the ET time series (both in-situ and simulated) also cause physically pointless, unreasonably high WUE values. So, we chose to limit the WUE range for the plots and analysis here between 0 and 25 gC mm⁻¹. But, as these measurements already show, WUE is a complex variable that depends on the variability of two (GPP and ET) measures which each have underlying uncertainty that we have underlined below. Therefore both, measured and simulated WUE should be compared with caution.

Generally, the WUE shows a weaker seasonal variability. With the bare eye, just the observed WUE seems to have a higher WUE during summer and a lower during winter, but at a much lower seasonal amplitude than the single GPP and ET variables. The simulated WUE on the other hand, shows the opposite behaviour: It rather rises during the winter, with very high peaks around the turn of the years, and it goes to a lower baseline in summer. This lower simulated summer WUE baseline is usually lower than the observed summer WUE. The hinted seasonal anti-correlation does not exist on a monthly basis. The resulting R² of 0.1 between the simulated and observed WUE suggests no relationship between the variability of the two. We therefore conclude that the simulated WUE is not able to represent observations. The apparent negative relationship between

seasonal WUE of simulations and observations might give hints on the underlying functional responses.

Figure 3-61. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) WUE (in g C mm⁻¹). Data for this site and variable was available from 2014 until 2018.

Simulation of Hyytiälä using the 1D-ICZ model

The Hyytiälä site has flux tower data measurements of CO₂ and latent heat fluxes from 1996 to 2020. For this site we performed one simulation for the period 1996-2020 using the 1D-ICZ model. The soil profile was defined to be at 60cm and it was discretized into seven nodes and six layers with a depth of 10cm each. No forest management e.g. harvest, tillage, addition of fertilizers, compost or manure was applied at Hyytiälä.

Initialization of the 1D-ICZ model – The model is driven by monthly time series input of precipitation, ET, Temperature, Photosynthetic Active Radiation (PAR) and nutrient inputs from atmospheric deposition. All the necessary data (Table 3-3) for the simulation were retrieved from FLUXNET and the eLTER Repository (B2Drop). The input time series of precipitation was calculated by summing up daily values and by converting them into monthly and to convert units from mm to m. The monthly time series of temperature and latent heat (LE) were retrieved intact from FLUXNET. However, the values of LE were converted from W m⁻² to m using the appropriate conversion (Appendix I). The input time series of PAR was calculated as the day time average by eliminating all the zeros and by taking the average of the remaining data. Regarding the nutrient inputs, we used available soil chemistry initial conditions for H⁺, NO₃N, NH₄N and precipitation chemistry monthly data for H⁺, NO₃N, NH₄N and PO₄P. For the nutrients Ca, Mg, Na, K, F, Al and SO₄S we also used the input and precipitation chemistry data of Zöbelboden since there were no such data for the Hyytiälä site.

Table 3-3. Input data retrieved from FLUXNET and eLTER Repository

Parameter name and description	Timestep	Units	Model
Precipitation	Monthly	m	HYDRUS-1D
Evapotranspiration	Monthly	m	HYDRUS-1D
Air temperature	Monthly	°C	HYDRUS-1D PROSUM
Bulk density	-	g cm ⁻³	HYDRUS-1D
	-	kg m ⁻³	CAST
Soil chemistry: H ⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺	Initial (month)	mol L ⁻¹	Excel Tool for HYDRUS-1D
Precipitation chemistry: H ⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺	Monthly	mol L ⁻¹	Excel Tool for HYDRUS-1D
Clay content (for each layer)	-	%	CAST
Silt-clay content (for each layer)	-	%	CAST
PAR (photosynthetic active radiation)	Monthly	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	PROSUM

Calibration of the 1D-ICZ model – Our primary aim was to calibrate the PROSUM sub-model (plant model) using the GPP from the flux tower measurements. Doing so, we were able to simulate the limiting factors of growth, the nutrient uptake and also, the C and N stocks for the leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. For the CAST sub-model, we only used TOC measurements in order to simulate the total SOC as we didn't have available Water Stable Aggregate (WSA) fractionation data to properly simulate the soil formation and structure. Then, we calibrated the geochemistry (IC, TOC, TN, PO₄P and H⁺) of both catchments using 1) soil water chemistry data measurements

from lysimeters in multiple pits and 2) runoff water chemistry data through weirs. For the Inorganic Carbon, we compared the simulated concentration of HCO_3^- with the IC measurements. For the Total Organic Carbon, we compared the sum of the simulated concentrations of oxalate, BIO and HUM with the TOC measurements. For the Total Nitrogen, we compared the sum of the simulated concentrations of NH_4^+ , NH_3 , NO_3^- and LMWN (Low Molecular Weight Nitrogen). The calibration of soil chemistry was conducted for the last (6th) soil layer (50-60cm). Once the model was calibrated, we used the simulation data to study the impact of drought on the response and resilience of the forested ecosystem.

Results – Hyytiälä 1D-ICZ

The 1D-ICZ model successfully simulated the GPP of the Hyytiälä forested ecosystem along with the growth limitations, the total C and N biomass, the nutrient uptake, the C and N stocks of leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. The primary limiting factors of growth were P and N. With the aim of calibrating GPP we firstly modified parameters associated with temperature and PAR. Then, we decreased the adsorption of PO_4P and also, adjusted the min and max C/N and C/P ratios of leaf and root to increase the available P in the soil. However, the adjustment of these parameters was not enough since it was observed the GPP for the first seven years were not simulated properly. This phenomenon was also observed during the calibration of GPP for the Zöbelboden site. It was due to nutrients (Al, Ca, K, Mg, Na) deposition measurements of Zöbelboden that were significantly lower than the rest of the months. To resolve this issue, we used the nutrient fluxes of the next seven years back-to-back and the GPP was successfully simulated (Figure 3-62). The RMSE between the monthly simulated and field data was 67.38 gC m^{-2} while the annual RMSE was 389.30 gC m^{-2} (or 35% of the mean annual GPP). Finally, the difference between the cumulative field and modelled GPP was $12,288.59 \text{ gC m}^{-2}$ which corresponds to 3% closure. These results suggest that the 1D-ICZ model is capable of simulating GPP while accounting correctly for the limiting factors, the nutrient fluxes, temperature and PAR.

Figure 3-64 presents the evolution of limiting factors for the growth of the forest. P, N, light and water were the most significant limiting factors. Figure 3-65 shows the evolution of total biomass of C and N over time (1996-2020). The total biomass of C increases throughout the simulation period while the total biomass of N remains stable. The nutrient uptake is shown in figure 3-66 with C and N uptake to be the highest. Figure 3-67 and 3-68 illustrates the C and N stocks of leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. Overall, C and N stocks of leaf, root and mycorrhizae fluctuate over time. In contrast, C and N stocks of wood increase and then stabilize. The average C and N stock of leaf are 15.8 mol m^{-2} and 1.52 mol m^{-2} respectively. The average C and N stocks of the wood are 179.4 mol m^{-2} and 0.62 mol m^{-2} respectively. The average C and N stock of root is 18.5 mol m^{-2} and 0.52 mol m^{-2} . Lastly, the average C stock of mycorrhizae is 10 mol m^{-2} .

Figure 3-62. Comparison of simulated GPP with flux tower measurements (1996-2020).

Figure 3-63. Comparison of cumulative simulated GPP with cumulative GPP measurements over the years.

Figure 3-64. Evolution of limiting factors to growth.

Figure 3-65. Total C and N biomass with time.

Figure 3-66. Simulated nutrient uptake with time.

Figure 3-67. Simulated C stock for leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae.

Figure 3-68. Simulated N stock for leaf, wood and root.

Geochemistry

The figures 3-69 to 3-78 present the comparison of solutes (IC, TOC, TN, PO₄P, H⁺) measurements of both catchments with the simulated solute concentrations. Regarding the ground runoff data, we retrieved data from Weir 1 and 2. Weir 1 is part of catchment No 1 and Weir 2 is part of catchment No 2. Lysimeters data from multiple pits were used for both catchments. More specifically, from catchment No 1 we used data from Pit50/2, Pit50/3 and Pit50/4 and from catchment No 2 we used data from Pit60/1, Pit60/2, Pit60/3 and Pit60/4. Pit name indicates the depth of the pit, i.e. the depth of mineral soil above bedrock. In each pit there are lysimeters in different depths that are indicated with /x, e.g. PIT50/1 is the topmost lysimeter of Pit50. This comparison was conducted for the sixth and last soil layer (50-60cm). From these diagrams it is clear that the 1D-ICZ model was able to simulate very successfully the solutes IC, TOC, TN, PO₄P and H⁺ of both catchments of Hyytiälä site.

Figure 3-69. Comparison of IC (HCO₃⁻) measurements (from weirs) with simulated IC for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-70. Comparison of IC (HCO_3^-) measurements (from pits) with simulated IC for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-71. Comparison of TOC measurements (from weirs) with simulated TOC for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-72. Comparison of TOC measurements (from pits) with simulated TOC for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-73. Comparison of TN measurements (from weirs) with simulated TN for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-74. Comparison of TN measurements (from pits) with simulated TN for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-75. Comparison of PO₄P measurements (from weirs) with simulated PO₄P for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-76. Comparison of PO₄P measurements (from pits) with simulated PO₄P for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-77. Comparison of H⁺ measurements (from weirs) with simulated H⁺ for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Figure 3-78. Comparison of H⁺ measurements (from pits) with simulated H⁺ for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time.

Soil formation and structure

Figure 3-79 shows the SOC of each soil layer during the period 1996-2020. Figures 3-80 to 3-82 presents the OC contained in silt-clay sized microaggregates (AC1), microaggregates (AC2) and macroaggregates (AC3) respectively. Figures 3-83 to 3-85 show the WSA mass contained in silt-clay sized microaggregates (<53 μm), microaggregates (53-250 μm) and macroaggregates (>250 μm). It is noted that there were no available WSA fractionation data in order to properly calibrate the CAST sub-model and thus, simulate the soil formation (aggregation and disaggregation) and soil structure. However, by using TOC measurements we were able to partially calibrate the CAST sub-model. Figure 3-79 shows that the observed SOC of each soil layer remains stable over time. Regarding the OC in aggregate fractions AC1, AC2 and AC3, OC contained in AC1 and AC3 appear to be relatively stable and OC contained in AC2 appears to be reduced over time. Moreover, the highest amount of OC is contained in aggregate fraction AC3 and the lowest in aggregate fraction AC1. It is suggested that in order to simulate soil formation and structure, soil sampling from the forested ecosystem of Hyytiälä and preparation for WSA procedure, sand correction procedure, microaggregate isolation procedure and chemical analysis should be conducted.

Figure 3-79. SOC for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-80. Organic carbon contained in silt-clay sized microaggregates (<53 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-81. Organic carbon contained in microaggregates (53-250 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-82. Organic carbon contained in macroaggregates (>250 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-83. Mass of WSA in silt-clay sized microaggregates (<53 μm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-84. Mass of WSA in microaggregates (53-250 µm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

Figure 3-85. Mass of WSA in macroaggregates (>250 µm) for each soil layer over time (1996-2020).

WUE and impact of drought analysis:

The WUE was estimated using the simulated GPP and the ET measurements. Figure 3-86 shows the monthly simulated WUE in kg m^{-3} and Figure 3-87 presents the average WUE over the years. During this process it was observed that some monthly values of WUE were very high ($16.6\text{--}85.1 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) due to the very low values of ET and thus, they were eliminated from the analysis. Overall, WUE over the years varies between 1.85 to 7.82 kg m^{-3} and has an average value of 4.82 kg m^{-3} .

Drought analysis was conducted using Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI). PDSI was calculated for the period 1996-2020 and it is presented in Figure 3-88. The impact of drought was accessed by estimating the Drought Index, the GPP Response Index and the Resilience Index for the extreme events of drought ($\text{PDSI} < -2.0$) during the 25year simulation period. Figure 3-89 shows the comparison between the Drought Index and the GPP Response Index and Figure 3-90 between the Drought Index and the Drought Resilience Index.

During the drought analysis, extreme events of drought were observed:

- From November 1996 to April 1998
- From June 1999 to September 1999
- From September 2002 to April 2004, and
- From July 2006 to November 2006

The results are similar to Zöbelboden and suggest that drought is directly impacting the GPP response and resilience in a positive way (Figures 3-89 and 3-90). More precisely, when the severity of drought increases so does the response and so does the resilience. These relationships are quite strong and the R^2 for the Drought versus GPP Response Index is 0.74 and for the Resilience Index 0.76. These results suggest that the forested ecosystem of Hyytiälä is responding in a positive way to extreme drought events and the ecosystem is resilient.

Figure 3-86. Simulated WUE for the period 1996-2020.

Figure 3-87. Average WUE over the years.

Figure 3-88. Simulated PDSI for the period 1996-2020.

Figure 3-89. Comparison of Drought Index to the GPP Response Index for Hyytiälä.

Figure 3-90. Comparison of Drought Index to the Drought Resilience Index for Hyytiälä.

Simulation of Hyytiälä using the CLM5-BGC model

Results – Hyytiälä CLM5-BGC

We again compared ET from the eddy covariance tower of the Hyytiälä station (Figure 3-91). From the in-situ station we had ET observations from 1996 until 2020. CLM5-BGC results ranged from 1995 until 2018, so that this analysis is limited to the years between 1996 and 2018. We aggregated the in-situ and simulated ET to monthly sums (mm month^{-1}) and plotted both time-series. A great difference is that CLM5 outputs included negative values, and the observed ET time-series did not. In all winters, the simulated ET trough was lower than 0 mm month^{-1} . Consequently, winter ET was constantly underestimated in the winter season during the whole study period. The spring and autumn transition periods seem to be very well represented, leading to a very high R^2 of 0.9. The peak summer ET was well simulated in the first half of the study period, from 1996 until 2009. The inter-annual fluctuations were captured well in that period, e.g. accurately simulating the transition from a lower summer ET peak in 1996 to a higher summer ET peak in 1997 and from a high summer ET peak in 2003 to a low summer ET peak in 2004. But importantly, summer ET peak in 1999 is quite overestimated and from 2002–2004 the summer ET peaks are slightly underestimated by CLM5-BGC compared to the in-situ observations. Then, from 2009 to 2018, there is a systematic underestimation of the summer ET peak by CLM5-BGC combined with an increased underestimation of winter ET. Rather than a misrepresentation of seasonal variability as seen above for the simulations of Zöbelboden, here the comparison suggests that simulated ET from CLM5-BGC missed a temporal increasing trend which is present in the observations. Further analysis should scrutinize missing concepts in the included long-term environmental drivers, their trends and the functional response of ecosystem processes in the model. Parameter and model structural improvements in CLM5-BGC should focus on the representation of the increasing ET trend in winter and summer in Hyytiälä.

Figure 3-91. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) ET (in mm month^{-1}). Data for this site and variable was available from 1996 until 2018.

The in-situ measured GPP time-series of the Hyttiälä station were also available from 1996 to 2020, and the simulations from 1995 until 2018, so that we could perform comparisons in the period between 1996–2018 (Figure 3-92). As already observed in the Zöbelboden GPP time-series comparison, we notice that simulated autumn, winter and spring GPP matches well with the observations, resulting in a high R^2 of 0.88. Just the rising spring GPP transition phase in the first year 1996 and in the last year 2018 were timed later in the simulations than the observations. But notably, the simulated summer GPP is generally lower than the in-situ measured summer GPP. The simulated summer GPP peaks are relatively stable across the years around $200 \text{ gC month}^{-1}$, while the summer peaks of in-situ measured GPP range between 200 and $310 \text{ gC month}^{-1}$. But the later years 2009–2018 show a generally higher level of the summer GPP peak, always above $250 \text{ gC month}^{-1}$ and reaching the maximum in summer 2013. This suggests an association to the observed ET trend (higher summer and winter ET in the later years). The in-situ greater base summer GPP, greater inter annual variability of the summer peaks and an increased summer GPP in the later years are not present in the CLM5-BGC simulations. The missing trend in both ET and GPP in the simulations reinforces the hypothesis of a missing vegetation functional response to environmental drivers. Especially the inclusion of rising atmospheric CO_2 and the vegetation response to it in the CLM5-BGC model should be investigated in detail.

Figure 3-92. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) GPP (in gC month^{-1}). Data for this site and variable was available from 1996 until 2018.

As indicated above, WUE is a sensitive variable as it depends on the covariability between ET and GPP. Even if both GPP and ET have nicely represented variabilities in the model (e.g. both have a high R^2) the WUE could be not well represented because small scale misrepresented dynamics in GPP and ET would magnify and greatly influence the representation of WUE. As explained before, we masked the time-series to positive ET and GPP values and $\text{WUE} < 25 \text{ gC mm}^{-1}$. Consequently, in Hyttiälä, simulated WUE values were masked every winter. But summer WUE appears to compare well between simulations and in-situ observations: Remarkable dynamics (small-scale transitions and peaks) in the summers of 1996, 2000, and 2001 are represented well in CLM5-BGC simulations. Also, the magnitude of summertime WUE compares well between simulations and in-situ observations. But in the simulations summer WUE constitute the troughs in

the time-series, while in the observations the peaks. Therefore, we conclude that the simulations of winter and summer ET and GPP should get improved in regard of the functional representation of WUE. But first, more comparative seasonal analysis is needed, with the same definitions of ET (containing negative values, i.e. condensation or not).

Figure 3-93. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) WUE (in g C mm^{-1}). Data for this site and variable was available from 1996 until 2018.

Simulation of Svartberget using the 1D-ICZ model

The Svartberget site has flux tower measurements for CO₂ and latent heat fluxes from 2014 to 2020. For this site, we performed one simulation for the period 2014-2020 using the 1D-ICZ model. The soil profile was defined to be at 60cm, meaning that it has seven nodes and six layers with a depth of 10cm for each layer. No forest management (e.g. harvest, tillage, addition of fertilizers, compost or manure) was applied to the Svartberget simulation.

Initialization of the 1D-ICZ model – The model is driven by monthly time series input of precipitation, ET, Temperature, Photosynthetic Active Radiation (PAR) and nutrient inputs from atmospheric deposition. All the necessary data (Table 3-4) for the simulation were retrieved from FLUXNET and the eLTER Repository (B2Drop). The input time series of precipitation was calculated by summing up daily values to monthly values and converting them from mm to m. The monthly time series of temperature, latent heat (LE) and PAR were retrieved from the FLUXNET database. ET was calculated from flux tower latent heat data (Appendix I). Monthly deposition data for K, NO₃N, NH₄N and PO₄P were used as input to the model and available stream chemistry (C2 station) data were used as initial conditions for soil Ca, K, Mg, Na, H⁺, NO₃N, and PO₄P. For all the other elements for which we did not have data of atmospheric deposition we used data from Zöbelboden. No data were available for soil structure, so we used the measurements of bulk density, clay and silt-clay content of the Hyytiälä station, because they have similar geology.

Table 3-4. Input data retrieved from FLUXNET and eLTER Repository

Parameter name and description	Timestep	Units	Model
Precipitation	Monthly	m	HYDRUS-1D
Evapotranspiration	Monthly	m	HYDRUS-1D
Air temperature	Monthly	°C	HYDRUS-1D PROSUM
Bulk density	-	g cm ⁻³	HYDRUS-1D
	-	kg m ⁻³	CAST
Stream chemistry: Ca, K, Mg, Na, H ⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻	Initial (month)	mol L ⁻¹	Excel Tool for HYDRUS-1D
Precipitation chemistry: K, NO ₃ ⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺ and PO ₄ ³⁻	Monthly	mol L ⁻¹	Excel Tool for HYDRUS-1D
Clay content (for each layer)	-	%	CAST
Silt-clay content (for each layer)	-	%	CAST
PAR (photosynthetic active radiation)	Monthly	μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	PROSUM

Calibration of the 1D-ICZ model – The field data we had to calibrate the model were the flux tower measurement of GPP (used to calibrate the PROSUM plant sub-model) and the stream chemistry data to calibrate the geochemistry. When we first ran the 1D-ICZ model we observed that there were no nutrient limitations to growth. Looking back to the input data we discovered that the deposition measurements of K, NO₃N, NH₄N and PO₄P were of an order of magnitude 10⁻⁴–10⁻³ mol L⁻¹. These values are unusually high compared to Zöbelboden and Hyytiälä precipitation chemistry data. These high deposition rates made it impossible to calibrate the stream chemistry, so it was necessary to decrease these values by 3 to 4 orders of magnitude. The TOC measurements were used to partially calibrate the CAST sub-model due to absence of fractionation data. Finally, the geochemistry (Ca, Na, Mg, K, NO₃N, PO₄P, SO₄S and H⁺) of the

forested sub-catchment C2 was calibrated using stream chemistry measurements. The calibration of soil chemistry was conducted for the last (6th) soil layer (50-60cm).

Results – Svartberget 1D-ICZ

Figure 3-94 to 3-100 present the PROSUM model GPP simulation results. The calibration of the model was not good primarily because of problems in the deposition data that affect growth limitations and biomass production as well as the lack of other required data (especially for soil initial conditions and soil structure data).

Figure 3-94. Comparison of simulated GPP with flux tower measurements (2014-2020).

Figure 3-95. Comparison of cumulative simulated GPP with cumulative GPP measurements over the years.

Figure 3-96. Evolution of limiting factor to growth.

Figure 3-97. Total C and N biomass with time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-98. Simulated nutrient uptake with time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-99. Simulated C stock for the leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae.

Figure 3-100. Simulated N stock for the leaf, wood and root.

Geochemistry

Figures 3-101 to 3-108 illustrate the comparison of solute (Na, Mg, K, Ca, H^+ , NO_3N , PO_4P and SO_4S) stream measurements with the simulated solute concentrations. This comparison was conducted for the sixth and last soil layer (50-60cm). From these diagrams it is clear that the 1D-ICZ model was able to simulate the solute transport of Na, H^+ , NO_3N and SO_4S . On the contrary, the model was unable to simulate Mg, K, Ca and PO_4P .

For the solutes (K, NO_3N , PO_4P) we had available deposition data but as mentioned before we had to decrease them by 3 to 4 orders of magnitude because the values were too high. Doing so, we were able to simulate NO_3N . Regarding Na, Mg, Ca, H^+ and SO_4S no data were available. So, we adjusted the input of Na based on the stream concentration and doing so, we observed that the calibration of Na was a success. Thus, we assumed that Na originates entirely from precipitation. The solute SO_4S also comes from precipitation and is successfully simulated by the model. For the rest of the solutes for which no measurements were available the calibration was not successful.

Figure 3-101. Comparison of Na stream measurements with simulated Na for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-102. Comparison of Mg stream measurements with simulated Mg for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-103. Comparison of K stream measurements with simulated K for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-104. Comparison of Ca stream measurements with simulated Ca for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-105. Comparison of H^+ stream measurements with simulated H^+ for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-106. Comparison of NO_3N stream measurements with simulated NO_3N for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-107. Comparison of PO₄P stream measurements with simulated PO₄P for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time (2014-2020).

Figure 3-108. Comparison of SO₄S stream measurements with simulated SO₄S for the 6th soil layer (50-60cm) over time (2014-2020).

Simulation of Svartberget using the CLM5-BGC model

Results – Svartberget CLM5-BGC

We also compared ET between in-situ measurements from an eddy covariance station at Svartberget with CLM5-BGC simulation outputs (Figure 3-109). The period for analysis was limited by the earliest available in-situ measurement (2014) and the end of forcing data for our simulations (2018). The original ET values from simulations and observations were converted to monthly sums (mm month^{-1}). Between 2017 and early 2018 we encountered missing values in the observation time-series that we masked out. We show the comparisons of those time-series in Figure 3-109. Again as the simulated ET time-series of Hyytiälä and Zöbelboden, ET here contains negative values during winter that correspond to condensation.

Consistent with the results from the other sites, we observe a high R^2 of 0.87 between simulated and observed ET in Svartberget. Especially the transition phases in spring and summer are well represented. The summer peaks in 2014, 2015 are of the same magnitude in simulations and observations. In the summer of 2016 CLM5-BGC underestimates the ET peak by 10 mm month^{-1} and in 2018 it overestimates the ET peak by more than 20 mm month^{-1} which constitutes an overestimation of about 25%. As observed at the other sites as well, winter ET is always underestimated in the simulations, but possibly just because of the inclusion of condensation as negative ET in the time-series. Further analysis will look into a comprehensive comparison of just winter ET between simulations and observations to determine the reason for the systematic underestimation. Longer time-series are needed to analyse functional responses of ecosystem ET in Svartberget.

Figure 3-109. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) ET (in mm month^{-1}). Data for this site and variable was available from 2014 until 2018.

Also for GPP, in Svartberget the analysis time-series are limited to the years 2014 until 2018 (Figure 3-110). Similar to the ET time-series, GPP data-gaps in 2017 and 2018 were masked from the analysis. The resulting data was aggregated to monthly sums (gC month^{-1}).

The time-series analysis of in-situ GPP resulted in a high R^2 of 0.89, especially the autumn transition from high to low GPP was well represented in all available years. The spring transition from low to high GPP was a bit delayed in the simulations as compared to the observations in the years 2014, 2016 and 2018. The GPP in year 2015 was especially well represented in the model outputs. In that year, spring transition is timed better and the simulated GPP peak is very close to the measured GPP (very slight overestimation). In all other available years (2014, 2016 and 2018) the summer peak GPP was overestimated by CLM5-BGC, especially in the first year (2014) and the last year (2018) where the overestimated peaks were 50% higher than the observations (over $300 \text{ gC month}^{-1}$ compared to $200 \text{ gC month}^{-1}$ in 2018). The large underestimation in 2018 is also present in the ET time-series, but not in 2014. Further investigations may look into the discrepancies of ET and GPP estimation mismatches and conclude on the resulting influence on the response of the WUE function. We encourage analysis with longer time-series for robust interpretations of trends and responses to changing environmental conditions.

Figure 3-110. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) GPP (in gC month^{-1}). Data for this site and variable was available from 2014 until 2018.

The WUE time-series for the analysis in Svartberget ranges from 2014 to 2018 (Figure 3-111). However, due to the data processing of excluding negative ET values in winter, WUE values higher than 25 gC mm^{-1} and data-gaps in 2017 and 2018, the time-series of simulations as well as of in-situ measurement show several gaps. As already observed at the other sites, summer WUE magnitude is estimated fairly in CLM5-BGC. The summer WUE functional dynamics in 2014 for example are represented well: there is an initial WUE peak, followed by a trough and another peak. This sequence is evident in both observations and simulation and is similarly present in 2015. The small peak in mid summer of 2016 is a bit overestimated by CLM5 but the similar evolution suggests that the simulation captures particular environmental influences on GPP, ET and the WUE function well. Again, the transition periods are not well represented because of the winter WUE values that are maxima in the simulations but minima in the observations. This again suggests there is a misrepresented relationship between summer to winter GPP and ET variability. It will be evaluated in more detailed analyses in the future. Generally, because of the sensitive nature of WUE time-series, specific functional responses to environmental drivers should be

investigated one by one. Those future results will be able to enhance discretization and model parametrization of functional vegetation groups and help assess the state of ecosystem performance now and in future.

Figure 3-111. Time-series plot of observed (in-situ, blue line) and simulated (CLM5-BGC, red line) WUE (in g C mm⁻¹). Data for this site and variable was available from 2014 until 2018.

3.3. WUE modelling with watershed scale models results

The final evaluation of this work deals with the assessment of the watershed scale models to evaluate the impact of drought to WUE and the GPP. Two different watershed models were used, the SWAT and the INCA-N models. SWAT was used to model the Koiliaris CZO in Greece while INCA-N was used to model Svartberget Catchment in Sweden covering in this way the two extremes of Europe.

WUE modelling at the Koiliaris CZO using SWAT

In this work we analysed the results from a simulation of Koiliaris CZO for an irrigated Orange grove landuse from 1980-2020. The monthly GPP, ET, WUE and PDSI monthly simulated time series are presented in Figure 3-112. The average annual simulated GPP was 7.9 kgC m^{-2} while the average annual ET was 957 mm y^{-1} . The average WUE was determined to 9.5 kgC m^{-3} of water. The PDSI for the region determined that we had eight medium to extreme drought events (PDSI less than -2).

Figure 3-112. Simulated time series of GPP, ET, WUE and PDSI for an orange grove at Koiliaris CZO.

The PDSI and the GPP time series were used to determine the drought response and resilience indices for the site. Table 3-5 presents the determination of the drought indices for the eight extreme drought events realized between 1980-2020. The number of consecutive months with PDSI below -2 range from 4 to 24 while the average PDSI during these periods ranged from -2.1 to -3.3. The Drought Index ranged from -8.2 to -59, with three events to have values less than -30. The GPP Response Index ranged from $7.1 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ to $12 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$. The resilience Index ranged

from 0.56 to -1.0, while the index for three out of the eight events was higher than 0.7 meaning that it reached 70% of the non-drought maximum growth.

Table 3-5. Determination of the drought indices, the GPP Response and Resilience Indexes for 8 medium to extreme drought events at Koiliaris CZO for an irrigated Orange grove.

No of months	Average PDSI	Drought Index	GPP Response index	GPP max	Resilience Index
6	-2.2	-13.4	11.4	1.2	0.94
4	-2.1	-8.2	7.1	0.72	0.56
14	-2.8	-38.8	12.0	1.3	1.0
12	-2.6	-31.2	9.2	0.84	0.66
5	-2.7	-13.4	11.2	1.08	0.84
24	-2.5	-59.0	7.8	0.81	0.63
5	-2.3	-11.6	6.6	0.73	0.57
5	-3.3	-16.4	8	0.85	0.66

Figures 3-113 presents a comparison of the Drought Index with GPP Response Index for all the drought events. Both the GPP Response and the Resilience Indices are not being affected by the increasing Drought duration and intensity. Irrigation is alleviating any possible drought effects. The results are consistent with the flux tower drought response we obtained from the other ecosystems.

Figure 3-113. Comparison of the Drought Index with a) GPP Response Index and b) Resilience for Koiliaris CZO drought events for an irrigated Orange grove.

WUE modelling at the Svartberget Catchment using INCA-N

The analysis presented here addresses two questions: (i) Can a catchment-scale water quality model be used to provide meaningful information about WUE in the boreal forest and (ii) what data sources are available to support modelling. We used a new version of the Integrated Catchments model for nitrogen (INCA-N) to simulate stream flows and nitrogen concentrations measured at the catchment outlet of the Svartberget (Krycklan) eLTER site. INCA-N is primarily a water quality model that also simulates some ecosystem processes. Catchment water use is simulated as actual evapotranspiration (AET) estimated using a Jensen-Haise/McGuinness formulation for potential evapotranspiration and modelled soil moisture. As the INCA-N model does not simulate primary productivity, we used modelled nitrogen (N) uptake by the plant community as a proxy for plant

growth. We were thus able to estimate WUE as the mass of N taken up by the plant community per unit AET. The model was calibrated to observations from 2008-2013 and applied using forcing data from 1998-2020. Between 1998 and 2020, there was a marked decrease in atmospheric N deposition and a co-occurring increase in air temperature. The latter contributed to a longer growing season and drier soils. Overall, there was a marked declining trend in modelled nitrogen uptake per unit AET over the course of the simulation (Figure 3-114). Our overall conclusion is that catchment scale water quality models can give insights into some representations of WUE at a landscape scale providing appropriate forcing and calibration data are available.

Figure 3-114. Long-term pattern in simulated water use efficiency (WUE) at the Svartberget eLTER site simulated using the INCA-N model. WUE is expressed as the mass of nitrogen taken up during the growing season (assumed to be a proxy for net primary productivity) divided by modelled AET (actual evapotranspiration).

Table 3-6. Data sets and sources used for model setup and calibration.

Dataset	Source	URL
Meteorology	SITES data portal	https://data.fieldsites.se/portal/#%7B%22filterCategories%22%3A%7B%22theme%22%3A%5B%22atmosphere%22%5D%2C%22station%22%3A%5B%22Svartberget%22%5D%2C%22location%22%3A%5B%22svartberget%22%5D%7D%7D
Deposition	SMHI data portal	https://luftwebb-miljoovervakning.smhi.se/SMHI-luftwebb-miljoovervakning-app/
Catchment properties	Primary literature	https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/wrcr.20520
Stream flow	Krycklan database	https://data.krycklan.se/
Stream chemistry	Krycklan database	https://data.krycklan.se/

Evaluation of ICOS data

While the original intent of this study had been to use data from the ICOS data portal for model setup and calibration, it turned out that these data could not be used for a number of reasons listed below. There was a poor correspondence between on-site meteorological measurements and the ICOS climate reanalysis products.

Figure 3-115. Comparison of ICOS reanalysis (vertical axis) and instrumental (horizontal axis) meteorological data for Svartberget. The left panel shows precipitation (mm/d) and the right panel shows air temperature (°C).

Meteorological reanalysis data from the ICOS portal were compared to instrumental measurements made in the catchment (Figure 3-115). There was an acceptable correspondence between ICOS (TA_ERA) and instrumental (TA) average daily air temperatures (Figure 3-115 left panel) but there was a poor match between ICOS (P_ERA) and instrumental (P) daily precipitation estimates (Figure 3-115 right panel). The ICOS reanalysis precipitation data showed a markedly different distribution than the instrumental data (Figure 3-116). There was a much higher proportion of zero precipitation days in the instrumental record than the reanalysis data (52% vs. 14%). There were a large number of days in the reanalysis data with small non-zero amounts of precipitation and the maximum daily precipitation was much lower in the reanalysis data than the instrumental data (26 mm vs. 45 mm). Given the discrepancy between reanalysis and instrumental records, and earlier work which showed the usability of instrumental records for predicting streamflow in the catchment (Ledesma, Futter, 2017), a decision was made to use instrumental meteorological data for modelling.

Figure 3-116. Cumulative distribution plots of ICOS reanalysis (P_ERA; blue) and instrumental (P; orange) data for Svartberget.

Deposition data from the ICOS portal exhibited a number of anomalies that could not be accounted for, making it necessary to evaluate alternative data sources (i.e., MATCH and EMEP). While either EMEP or MATCH deposition products would have been suitable, the latter were used as they were less computationally demanding. The stream flow and chemistry data available from the ICOS data portal were not sufficient for model calibration; stream flows were not available for all stations and not all nitrogen species were reported in the ICOS dataset.

The ICOS dataset included latent heat fluxes which we originally planned to use for comparison to the modelled INCA-N evapotranspiration estimates. Unfortunately, here were anomalies in the heat flux data. While quality control checks were passed, it appeared that the data were anomalous for at least one year (Figure 3-117).

Figure 3-117. Latent Heat fluxes from the ICOS data portal for Svartberget.

Trends in Forcing Data

Daily air temperatures displayed a consistent annual pattern with cold winters and cool summers (Figure 3-118). When these data were summarized to an annual time scale, there was a clear increase in annual average temperature with the greatest warming occurring in the spring (Figure 3-119).

Figure 3-118. Daily average air temperature at Svartberget.

Figure 3-119. Annual average and average spring monthly temperatures at Svartberget.

There were no overall trends in either total precipitation or the fraction of precipitation falling as snow (Figure 3-120). A combination of no change in precipitation and an increase in air temperature is likely to lead to drier soils (Kupec et al., 2021). Drier soils will, in turn reduce amounts of AET.

Figure 3-120. Total annual precipitation (blue) and fraction of precipitation falling as snow (orange) at Svartberget between 1991 and 2020.

Modelled MATCH deposition of both oxidized (nitrate) and reduced (ammonium) N declined during the model application period (Figure 3-121). Year on year variation in deposition amounts appears to be related to precipitation amount but the overall trend likely reflects reductions in emissions.

Figure 3-121. MATCH modelled annual deposition ($\text{kgN ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$) at Vindeln / Svartberget.

INCA-N Calibration

The model was calibrated to observations of flow, nitrate ammonia and DON at the C16 Krycklan catchment outlet for 1/1/2008 to 31/12/2013 using an automated parameter space exploration (Futter et al., 2014) and the Kling Gupta efficiency (KGE) statistic for assessing performance of individual parameter sets. For the final calibration presented here, KGE values of 0.92, 0.57, 0.29 and 0.36 are for flow, nitrate, ammonia and DON respectively (Figures 3-122 and 3-123).

Figure 3-122. Modelled (blue) and observed (red) streamflow at site C16, the Krycklan catchment outlet.

Figure 3-123. Modelled and observed concentrations of nitrogen species at site C16, the Krycklan catchment outlet.

INCA-N Results

Overall, there was good correspondence between the ICOS latent heat fluxes (LEE) and modelled daily actual evapotranspiration (AET) (Figure 3-124). Modelled AET generally started slightly later than measured positive latent heat fluxes and there was more day to day variation in the modelled AET. Both the measured and modelled time series suggested a decline in intensity between 2014 and 2020. Patterns of N uptake and immobilisation showed some evidence of a decline over time (Figure 3-125).

LE_CORR and AET

Figure 3-124. Latent heat fluxes (blue) and catchment-scale modelled actual evapotranspiration (orange).

Plant Uptake and Immobilisation

Figure 3-125. N uptake and immobilisation over time.

4. Synthesis and Conclusions

The eLTER PLUS Project, Work Package 8 aimed to explore how long-term biodiversity, biogeochemistry, hydrology and socio-ecology data from the eLTER network can provide the necessary holistic understanding of the ecosystem response to environmental and societal pressures. WP8 focuses on assessing the capacity of data provision of eLTER Sites to evaluate environmental impacts using the Whole System Approach. In particular task 8.3 aimed to improve the knowledge of the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience. Data from 10 well-instrumented sites that cross climatic, geological and socio-ecological regions were used to test resilience indicators. The overall objective of Task 8.3 is to address the following scientific question: “*What is the impact of drought events on ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) and resilience, and the relationships between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience?*”

Field data and integrated models were used to calculate the ecosystem WUE of sites to:

- Assess the impact of drought events on the WUE of ecosystems
- Analyze the resilience of the ecosystems with respect to their ability to recover single & multiple droughts
- Assess the relationship between WUE, soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience and develop mitigation measures for drought adverse impacts
- Assess the strengths and weaknesses of the RI-design to derive resilience indicators

Our methodology followed a three-prong approach:

- **Flux tower Eddy Covariance long term data** were used to assess the impact of droughts on WUE. Ten well instrumented sites with good availability of long-term data as well as good spatial distribution so the whole European continent is covered were selected for this analysis.
- Two **integrated models** the **1D-ICZ** and the **CLM5.0** models that simulate the plant-soil-water system were used to assess the relationship between WUE and soil structure, plant productivity and ecosystem resilience. For this analysis, in addition to flux tower data, data regarding vegetation, soil stocks of C, N, P, K, lysimeter chemistry, atmospheric chemistry and fertilization loadings were utilized to calibrate the models. Three sites (Zöbelboden, Austria; Hyytiälä, Finland; Svartberget, Sweden) were selected with the best available data.
- Finally, two **watershed scale** models, **SWAT** and **INCA** were used to assess the impact of droughts at the basin scale. Additional hydrologic data and river and groundwater chemistry data were required for the calibration of the models. Two different sites, Koiliaris CZO in Greece and Svartberget, Sweden were used for the simulations of SWAT and INCA-N respectively.

The methodology aimed at assessing how forested ecosystems respond to drought across Europe using flux tower eddy covariance field data and then examine if 1D integrated models and watershed models can capture the ecosystem response. Given that very few sites have long time series of flux tower data, this study is assessing the capability of integrated and watershed scale models to reconstruct historical impacts of drought events in a reanalysis exercise.

Flux tower Eddy Covariance Analysis – The monthly GPP, ET and WUE flux tower data along with the PDSI were used to determine drought indices for each site for various drought periods and then evaluate the Response and Resilience Indices. Given that there was no correlation between PDSI and WUE or ET, in this study drought indices were defined based on the response of GPP, the productivity of the forested ecosystem. The impact of drought on GPP, was estimated using the **Drought Response Index** and the **Resilience Index**. The Drought Response Index is the relationship between the Drought Index and the GPP Response Index. The Drought Index is defined as (Number of months that PDSI is less than -2.0) * (Average PDSI) during those months)

and the GPP Response Index is the total of monthly GPP the month after the drought period for a year. So, the Drought Response Index shows what was the total GPP productivity the year after a moderate to extreme drought occurred. The trend of the relationship between the Drought Index and the GPP Response Index illustrates the trend of the ecosystem response to drought events. Drought Resilience Index is the maximum GPP during the year after the end of the drought to the max GPP during the years without drought. The objective of this analysis was to identify the response of forested ecosystem productivity across the continent to drought events as well as the resilience of the ecosystems to drought (meaning that they are capable of achieving maximum growth after the drought event).

There were 25 extreme drought events realized at the 10 stations that allowed the determination of the drought indices. The number of consecutive months with PDSI below -2 range from 2 in Brasschaat to 29 in Yatir while the average PDSI during these periods ranged from -2.0 at Zöbelboden to -3.16 at Renon. The Drought Index ranged from -4.36 to -81.78, however only 4 events had values less than -40 across all sites. The GPP Response Index ranged from 676 g m⁻² y⁻¹ at Yatir to 2243 g m⁻² y⁻¹ at Wüstebach. Only the two events at Yatir had an annual growth less than 900 g m⁻². The resilience Index ranged from 0.58 to 1.0, while for 22 out of the 25 events the index was higher than 0.7 meaning that it reached 70% of the non-drought maximum growth.

The results of this analysis showed that the GPP Response is decreasing as the Drought duration and intensity are increasing (Figure 4-1). This can be observed both at the European level (including all the events together) as well as at the regional levels. However, it should be noted that at the low drought index events we have a high variability of the GPP response. On the other hand, we do not observe any significant trends in the impact of the intensity of drought on the Resilience of the system to reach maximum growth for Europe as a whole. It appears that all forested ecosystems are quite resilient to drought events regardless of the location. These results can be confirmed if we plot drought events greater than -25 drought index (Figure 4-1). Eliminating the less intense 17 events, the relationship between drought index and GPP response becomes more pronounced (R^2 of 0.63), decreasing at a rate of 138 g m⁻² y⁻¹ for every -10 units increase of the drought index. While the resilience index does not show any trend with the average resilience index to be at 75%.

It is important to mention at this point that the EC-GPP fluxes of Zöbelboden (not measured but derived from the EC measurements using flux partitioning) are not derived with the same methodology as the other sites that follow the ICOS methodology. The EC-GPP fluxes are responding to the short-term and average monthly dynamics, because the GPP model is being fitted to each month using data from all years. This means that the EC-GPP fluxes aren't suitable for analysis looking at drought response and recovery. For this, we would need to parameterize for each month of each year, or be even more resolved than this, which most sites could do but for the Zöbelboden site this wasn't possible due to low levels of data retention. With such parameterization in time, one can implicitly derive legacy effects of drought. However, in a certain analysis that was conducted by the Environment Agency of Austria, such dynamics cannot be seen, and if they were seen it is simply to coincidence with the driving weather variables R_g and VPD. Despite these concerns, it was chosen to keep these two datapoint in the analysis because the results were consistent with the response of other sites in central Europe. In addition, the Drought Index values were low (less than -25) and did not affect the trend analysis. On the other hand, the GPP estimates can be used for the calibration of the models for the Zöbelboden site.

Figure 4-1. Comparison of the Drought Index with a) GPP Response Index and b) Resilience for all the sites and drought events greater than -25 of drought index.

Integrated Model Analysis With the 1D-ICZ

Zöbelboden – The 1D-ICZ model successfully simulated the GPP of the Zöbelboden forested ecosystem along with the growth limitations, the total C and N biomass, the nutrient uptake, the C and N stocks of leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. The RMSE between the monthly simulated and field data was 80.12 gC m^{-2} while the annual RMSE was 247.55 gC m^{-2} (or 22% of the mean annual GPP). Finally, the difference between the cumulative field and modelled GPP was $3,302.33 \text{ gC m}^{-2}$ which corresponds to 10% closure. These results suggest that the 1D-ICZ model is capable of simulating GPP while accounting correctly for the limiting factors, the nutrient fluxes, temperature and PAR. The WUE was estimated by using the simulated GPP and the simulated ET over the simulated period 1996-2020. WUE varies between 1.95 and 5.45 kg m^{-3} and has an annual average of 3.67 kg m^{-3} and the results were similar to flux tower estimates.

The 1D-ICZ model was able to simulate the solute transport of F, K, Na, NH_4N , NO_3N and SO_4S quite well while for the simulations of Ca, Mg and H^+ the model was over or under predicting. Deposition data were available for Ca, K, Mg, Na, NH_4N , NO_3N , H^+ , and SO_4S but not for F. It was assumed that F originates entirely from precipitation, and thus the input values for boundary conditions were set to be the same order of magnitude as the soil measurements. The reason why solutes Ca and Mg couldn't be simultaneously simulated properly has to do with the weathering formulation of the model. The sub-model SAFE that simulates weathering processes includes six minerals in which one of them is dolomite and it does not include one of the primary minerals of Zöbelboden geology, limestone. If limestone was to be added in the model, the weathering of dolomite would simulate Mg concentrations and then the weathering of limestone would provide the additional Ca needed for the simulation of Ca. This would also correct the pH simulation. In the near future we intend to modify the code of sub-model SAFE and the process of limestone weathering.

Drought analysis was conducted using Palmer's Drought Severity Index (PDSI). PDSI was calculated for the period 1996-2020. Drought impact to plant growth was assessed by estimating the Drought Index, the GPP Response Index and the Resilience Index for the extreme drought events ($\text{PDSI} < -2.0$) during the 25year simulation period.

The analysis of drought for the period 1996-2020 showed that drought is directly impacting GPP and in particular the GPP response and resilience in a positive way. More precisely, when the severity of drought increases so does the response and so does the resilience. These relationships

are quite strong and the R^2 for the Drought versus GPP Response Index is 0.73 and for the Resilience Index 0.67. These results suggest that the forested ecosystem of Zöbelboden is responding in a positive way to extreme drought events and the ecosystem is resilient. This trend is different with the one produced by all droughts from the 10 sites using the flux tower data, however it is the same if we examine only the Zöbelboden droughts. The reason for this difference is that all but one of the Zöbelboden droughts from 1996-2020 have Drought Index values less than -30 which means that they are in the low intensity drought, an area with great variability in the GPP response.

A scenario of addition of organic matter (compost) was performed in order to assess the impact of soil structure and fertility to WUE. According to the 1D-ICZ model, the litterfall varies between 6.1 and 14.6 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ and has an average value of 9.6 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹. So, for this scenario the addition of 10 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ that is evenly distributed during the months between October to January (2.5 tC ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) was selected. The additional SOM was added in the form of compost. The results illustrate how SOM addition improves soil structure and soil dynamics by increasing the amount of carbon sequestered in the upper soil layer, the WSA content and by decreasing the bulk density of the soil and the porosity which in turn increase the water holding capacity of the soil.

Hyytiälä – The 1D-ICZ model successfully simulated the GPP of the Hyytiälä forested ecosystem along with the growth limitations, the total C and N biomass, the nutrient uptake, the C and N stocks of leaf, wood, root and mycorrhizae. The primary limiting factors of growth were P and N. The RMSE between the monthly simulated and field data was 67.38 gC m⁻² while the annual RMSE was 389.30 gC m⁻² (or 35% of the mean annual GPP). Finally, the difference between the cumulative field and modelled GPP was 12,288.59 gC m⁻² which corresponds to 3% closure. These results suggest that the 1D-ICZ model is capable of simulating GPP while accounting correctly for the limiting factors, the nutrient fluxes, temperature and PAR. It was also shown that the 1D-ICZ model was able to simulate very successfully the solutes IC, TOC, TN, PO₄P and H⁺ of both catchments of Hyytiälä site. The WUE over the years varies between 1.85 to 7.82 kg m⁻³ and has an average value of 4.82 kg m⁻³. Finally, drought analysis results are similar to Zöbelboden and suggest that drought is directly impacting the GPP response and resilience in a positive way. More precisely, when the severity of drought increases so does the response and so does the resilience. These relationships are quite strong and the R^2 for the Drought versus GPP Response Index is 0.74 and for the Resilience Index 0.76. These results suggest that the forested ecosystem of Hyytiälä is responding in a positive way to extreme drought events and the ecosystem is resilient.

Svartberget – The field data we had to calibrate the model were the flux tower measurement of GPP and the stream chemistry data to calibrate the geochemistry. There were deposition measurements of K, NO₃N, NH₄N and PO₄P available. However, the values were orders of magnitude higher than expected compared to Zöbelboden and Hyytiälä precipitation chemistry data. These high deposition rates made it impossible to calibrate the stream chemistry, so it was necessary to decrease these values by 3 to 4 orders of magnitude. The calibration of the model was not good primarily because of problems in the deposition data that affect growth limitations and biomass production as well as the lack of other required data (especially for soil initial conditions and soil structure data).

Integrated Model Analysis with CLM5.0

Zöbelboden – CLM5-BGC was able to capture the overall seasonal variations and ET changes in spring and autumn. The GPP flux was more accurately simulated at this site, with well agreeing minimal winter GPP values of CLM5-BGC with observations. However, summer peaks of both, ET and GPP are not well simulated, showing underestimations of GPP and overestimations of ET. This may be due to more structural problems CLM5-BGC has with simulating the eco-hydrology of karstic sites, or default vegetation parameters misrepresenting summer peak conditions. In future, seasonal decomposition of the time-series and multi-variate analysis of seasonal environmental factors might yield insights how to improve the CLM5-BGC model at the Zöbelboden site.

Hyytiälä – In the case of the Hyytiälä site, ET peaks in summer are modelled better than for Zöbelboden, but winter ET is still generally underestimated by CLM5-BGC. On top of that, there is an apparent trend in the observed ET that is not simulated by CLM5-BGC. The trend is also present for the observed GPP variable, and again not evident from the CLM5-BGC simulations. For Hyytiälä, future research will look at the representation of long-term CO₂ and VPD influence and evaluate the specific GPP and ET response to those long-term trends in the model.

Svartberget – The simulations of Svartberget in CLM5-BGC are showing well-fitting variation and summer peaks of ET when compared to in-situ observations. As with the other sites, winter ET is generally underestimated. Similarly, GPP is also well modelled at this site, but shows underestimated summer peaks. For a more detailed analysis, longer time series are of need, so that potential long-term trends and systematic modelling errors can be estimated robustly.

Watershed Model Analysis

WUE modelling at the Koiliaris CZO using SWAT – In this work we analysed the results from a simulation of Koiliaris CZO for an irrigated Orange grove landuse from 1980-2020. The average annual simulated GPP was 7.9 kgC m⁻² while the average annual ET was 957 mm y⁻¹. The average WUE was determined to 9.5 kgC m⁻³ of water. The PDSI for the region determined that we had eight medium to extreme drought events (PDSI less than -2). The PDSI and the GPP time series were used to determine the drought response and resilience indices for the site. The number of consecutive months with PDSI below -2 range from 4 to 24 while the average PDSI during these periods ranged from -2.1 to -3.3. The Drought Index ranged from -8.2 to -59, with three events showing values less than -30. The GPP Response Index ranged from 7.1 kg m⁻² y⁻¹ to 12 kg m⁻² y⁻¹. The resilience Index ranged from 0.56 to -1.0, while the index for three out of the eight events was higher than 0.7 meaning that it reached 70% of the non-drought maximum growth. Both the GPP Response and the Resilience Indices are not being affected by the increasing Drought duration and intensity. Irrigation is alleviating any possible drought effects. The results are consistent with the flux tower drought response we obtained from the other ecosystems.

WUE modelling at the Svartberget Catchment using INCA-N – The INCA-N simulations were able to satisfactorily reproduce flows and instream nitrogen concentrations. Model results suggested a decline in actual evapotranspiration during the period of simulation. This was corroborated by the ICOS latent heat data. The model also suggested a decline in net plant

nitrogen uptake. This, and its consequences for forest carbon accumulation, are worthy of further investigation.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the synthesis of the results presented above, several overarching conclusions and recommendations can be made:

1. Flux tower data analysis indicate a significant resilience to moderate to extreme drought events of forested ecosystems throughout Europe. In addition, the GPP Response is decreasing as the Drought duration and intensity are increasing. This can be observed both at the European level (including all the events together) as well as at the regional levels. However, it should be noted that at the low drought index events we have a high variability of the GPP response. These results can be confirmed if we plot drought events greater than -25 drought index. Eliminating the less intense 17 events, the relationship between drought index and GPP response becomes more pronounced (R^2 of 0.63), decreasing at a rate of $138 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for every -10 units increase of the drought index. While the resilience index does not show any trend with the average resilience index to be at 75%.
2. It is important to mention at this point that the EC-GPP fluxes of Zöbelboden (not measured but derived from the EC measurements using flux partitioning) are not derived with the same methodology as the other sites that follow the ICOS methodology. The EC-GPP fluxes are responding to the short-term and average monthly dynamics, because the GPP model is being fitted to each month using data from all years. This means that the EC-GPP fluxes aren't suitable for analysis looking at drought response and recovery. For this, we would need to parameterize for each month of each year, or be even more resolved than this, which most sites could do but for the Zöbelboden site this wasn't possible due to low levels of data retention. With such parameterization in time, one can implicitly derive legacy effects of drought. However, in a certain analysis that was conducted by the Environment Agency of Austria, such dynamics cannot be seen, and if they were seen it is simply to coincidence with the driving weather variables R_g and VPD. Despite these concerns, it was chosen to keep these two datapoint in the analysis because the results were consistent with the response of other sites in central Europe. In addition, the Drought Index values were low (less than -25) and did not affect the trend analysis. On the other hand, the GPP estimates can be used for the calibration of the models for the Zöbelboden site.
3. The 1D-ICZ model is capable of simulating successfully the primary production of the forested ecosystems and their Water Use Efficiency. In addition, it can correctly simulate the geochemistry of the unsaturated zone as well as the concentrations of solutes leaching to groundwater and the stream. These simulations are subject to appropriate deposition time series as well as soil characteristics and nutrient fractionation in the various aggregate sizes. These data constrain the model and assure proper simulation of the biogeochemical processes. Missing or erroneous data result in poor simulations as it was the case of Svartberget.
4. It is highly recommended that sites incorporate in their measurement cycles water stable fractionation procedures as well as measurements of carbon and nutrient content in the different fractions of the water stable aggregates. In this way the soil carbon and nutrient sequestration and soil structure module of the 1D-ICZ model can be constraint with field data and increase the validity of both the plant module as well as the geochemical module results.

5. The CLM5-BGC was able to capture the overall seasonal variations and ET changes for all three sites. The GPP flux was more accurately simulated at the Zöbelboden site compared to the other two.
6. Overall, this study showed that field scale models can adequately simulate the impacts of drought on forested ecosystems. Both the 1D-ICZ and the CLM5.0 were able to simulate the field data as well as identify the needs in additional measurements at each site. This information is very valuable for the development of the eLTER RI in terms of defining Standard Operating variables necessary to address the Whole System Approach.
7. Both the SWAT and the INCA-N watershed scale models were also able to simulate plant growth in agricultural and forested ecosystems respectively and assess the impact of drought on the water use efficiency of the vegetation. The results are consistent with the flux tower analysis, suggesting biogeochemical models can be used successfully to address changes in ecosystem services as part of the Whole System Approach.
8. All of the data needed to setup and calibrate the INCA-N model could be obtained from publicly accessible open data sources. However, it was not possible to obtain all the necessary data from any single data provider. This highlights both the challenges and opportunities when attempting to work from a WAILS (whole system) perspective. The need to source, manipulate and apply data from multiple sources is a challenge but it is a road map for the opportunities for virtual co-location when data from multiple sources are presented in a single portal. Further exploration of the possibilities for using portals to combine site level data from multiple disparate sources could lead to more timely modelling results and decision support.

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Appendix I. Data manipulation procedures for time series analysis.

List of Parameters:

- GPP (Gross Primary Production)
- ET (Evapotranspiration)
- WUE (Water Use Efficiency)
- PDSI (Palmer's Drought Severity Index)
- SM (Soil Moisture)

Dataset

Source: <https://fluxnet.org/data/fluxnet2015-dataset/fullset-data-product/>

1. GPP (Gross Primary Production): from Daytime partitioning method, reference selected from GPP versions using model efficiency (MEF). The MEF analysis is repeated for each time aggregation.

GPP_DT_VUT_REF

- DD (daily) calculated from half-hourly data ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) average from daily data ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)

2. NEE (Net Ecosystem Exchange): using Variable Ustar Threshold (VUT) for each year, reference selected on the basis of the model efficiency (MEF). The MEF analysis is repeated for each time aggregation.

NEE_VUT_REF

- DD (daily) calculated from half-hourly data ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) average from daily data ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)

3. Quality flag for NEE_VUT_REF (fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data)

NEE_VUT_REF_QC

- DD (daily) fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data (nondimensional)
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data (average from daily data) (nondimensional)

4. LE Latent heat flux, gapfilled using MDS method

LE_F_MDS

- DD (daily) calculated from half-hourly data (W m^{-2})
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) average from daily data (W m^{-2})

5. Quality flag for LE_F_MDS

LE_F_MDS_QC

- DD (daily) fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data (nondimensional)
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data (average from daily data) (nondimensional)

6. TA Air temperature, gapfilled using MDS method

TA_F_MDS

- DD (daily) average from half-hourly data (degC)
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) average from daily data (degC)

7. TA_F_MDS_DAY

8. Ecosystem Respiration, from Daytime partitioning method, reference selected from RECO versions using model efficiency (MEF). The MEF analysis is repeated for each time

aggregation

RECO_DT_VUT_REF

- DD (daily) calculated from half-hourly data ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) average from daily data ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)

9. SWC (Soil Water Content) gapfilled with MDS (numeric index “#” increases with the depth, 1 is shallowest)

SWC_F_MDS_#

- DD (daily) average from half-hourly data (%)
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) average from daily data (%)

10. Quality flag for SWC_F_MDS_#

SWC_F_MDS_#_QC

- DD (daily) fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data (nondimensional)
- WW-MM (weekly-monthly) fraction between 0-1, indicating percentage of measured and good quality gapfill data (average from daily data) (nondimensional)

Evapotranspiration Calculation

Source: Allen, R. G., Pereira, L. S., Raes, D., & Smith, M. (1998). Crop evapotranspiration - Guidelines for computing crop water requirements. FAO Irrigation and drainage Paper 56. <http://www.fao.org/3/x0490e/x0490e00.htm>

Evapotranspiration (**ET**) can be calculated from latent heat (**LE**) by dividing by latent heat of vaporization (λ)

$$ET = \frac{LE}{\lambda}$$

This assumes density of water equal to 1000 kg m^{-3} . Latent heat of vaporization is the amount of energy needed to change a unit mass of water from liquid to water vapor. With LE and λ in units of $\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{T}^{-1}$ and MJ kg^{-1} , respectively, ET is in units of $\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{T}^{-1}$ which is equal to depth of water in mm T^{-1} . Latent heat of vaporization varies slightly with temperature, but is often set to 2.45 MJ kg^{-1} which is the value for an air temperature of $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Allen et al. (1998) also provides an equation for calculating λ with air temperature variation:

$$\lambda = 2.501 - (2.361 \times 10^{-3}) \times T_a$$

where, T_a is air temperature in $^\circ\text{C}$ and λ is in MJ kg^{-1} .

The evapotranspiration rate is converted to mm day^{-1} from $\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$ as follows:

$$ET \text{ (Evapotranspiration)} = \frac{LE \text{ (Latent heat flux)}}{\lambda \text{ (Latent heat of vaporization)}} = \frac{LE}{\lambda} \left(\frac{W/m^2}{MJ/kg} \right) = 0.0864 \cdot \frac{LE}{\lambda} \left(\frac{mm}{day} \right)$$